

The National Physical Activity and Sedentary Behaviour Guidelines for Ireland for People Living with Chronic Conditions

**Final Research Report
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Executive Summary

To extend the National Physical Activity and Sedentary Behaviour Guidelines for Ireland 'Every Move Counts', the Health Service Executive (HSE) commissioned South East Technological University (SETU) to develop Ireland's first population-specific Physical Activity and Sedentary Behaviour Guidelines for people living well with chronic conditions.

This project includes an evidence review, stakeholder input and consensus, and then a summary process as part of this commissioning to develop these Physical Activity and Sedentary Behaviour Guidelines for people with chronic conditions. In this regard, this document is the accompanying research report that details, identified evidence gaps, development of evidence-informed guidance, and development of practical messaging for end-users with chronic conditions, health and social care professionals, and physical activity professionals. As a result of the development process, messaging for policy and decision makers are also included within this report.

A five-stage, mixed-methods process was used from August 2024 to February 2025, this included the following;

1. Evidence review

The evidence review included a narrative summary of guidelines and international guidelines, key position statements and consensus papers, and recent relevant reviews to inform 'Draft Guidelines/Recommendations', including 'Condition Specific Considerations'.

2. Drafting: Project team

The project team provided iterative feedback on the evidence review and initial drafts of the Guidelines and Messages. This group also identified additional evidence, and contextualised findings for Ireland, thus further shaping tone, structure, and content.

3. Consultation

Two anonymous online surveys were disseminated to people with chronic conditions, and health, social care, physical activity professionals. End users rated Draft Messages for practicality, clarity, and informativeness; professionals assessed clarity, appropriateness, and messaging relevance. Qualitative feedback highlighted areas for refinement in relation to areas such as clarity, tone and inclusivity.

4. National Stakeholder Meeting

Based on feedback from Stage 3, key stakeholders (academics, health, provider and advocacy groups) convened, and were facilitated to refine the Guidelines in Stage 4. Stakeholders focused on areas including enhancing specificity within public health scope, ensuring relevance and comprehensiveness, addressing needs of the populations of interest.

5. Consolidation and Refinement

Feedback from all stages was synthesised iteratively into final Guidelines, Good Practice Statements, Population Specific Considerations and Messages. Final revisions reflected feedback from stakeholder consultation while fitting within public health guidelines parameters.

This process has within a number of key strengths. These guidelines provide clear, practical recommendations to support physical activity among individuals living with chronic conditions. They recognise heterogeneity of the potential target populations, and indeed differing context, offering support for both individuals and professionals. The messaging within further promotes physical activity as a tool for self-management, addressing risk perceptions and emphasising the need for monitoring and an individualised approach.

While maintaining a broad public health perspective, the guidelines offer specific guidance relevant to various chronic conditions and stages of progression and recovery. Separate, targeted messaging for individuals, health professionals, and physical activity providers ensures relevance across roles. Policy-level recommendations advocate for systemic change through investment in infrastructure, workforce training, and inclusive community programs. The organic development and take-up of these Guidelines relies on effective dissemination and ongoing evaluation at scale.

This report outlines the process of developing National Physical Activity and Sedentary Behaviour Guidelines for people living well with chronic conditions, to accompany the National Physical Activity and Sedentary Behaviour Guidelines for Ireland, 'Every Move Counts'. The development of these Guidelines represents a significant advance in inclusive public health policy. Through a rigorous process, these guidelines have been shaped by high quality evidence and the input of a large number of key stakeholders reflecting the community of people living with chronic conditions in Ireland and relevant professionals working in practice and policy.

Introduction

The first National Physical Activity Guidelines for Ireland were published by the HSE in 2009 (1). These guidelines provided the foundation to promote physical activity in Ireland, however it did not include guidelines for sedentary behaviour, nor guidelines tailored for people living with chronic conditions. In 2020, the World Health Organisation (WHO) also published an update to their guidelines, included recommendations on sedentary behaviour and specific guidelines for people living with chronic conditions(2,3). Consequent to this, the HSE published updated guidelines: *Every Move Counts* National Physical Activity and Sedentary Behaviour Guidelines for Ireland (4). *Every Move Counts* also included messages for public and professional audiences designed to support the translation of the guidelines into practice. Within these updated guidelines, recommendations were put forward to include specific national level physical activity guidelines for people with chronic conditions. Consequently, The HSE commissioned researchers at South East Technological University (SETU) to extend *Every Move Counts* to develop physical activity and sedentary behaviour guidelines and messages for people living with chronic disease in Ireland.

Physical activity conveys significant health benefits both generally (5,6), and particularly to people living with long-term or chronic conditions (7–9). Across the lifespan, physical activity and reduced level of sedentary behaviour are associated with better mortality outcomes (10). Among a considerable number of chronic conditions, physical activity can slow certain disease progression, prevent further complications and the development of comorbidities, relieve symptoms, support disease management, enhance functional capacity and improve quality of life (9,11). Physical activity for these populations are generally safe and outweigh the health risks of sedentary behaviour, which research has identified in recent decades (12).

Despite this, people living with chronic conditions tend to be significantly less active than people without a chronic conditions (13). Fear of exercise-related risks is a barrier to physical activity participation among many living with chronic conditions (14). Concern that physical activity may aggravate symptoms or induce complications have been reported by people living with chronic conditions. Evidence from relevant healthcare contexts shows that many healthcare professionals may lack knowledge and confidence in promoting physical activity to these populations (15,16). National physical activity guidelines serve as recommendations, providing consensus on the scientific evidence, and raise awareness and knowledge of the health benefits of physical activity among different groups.

Development Process

Overview

The development of National Physical Activity and Sedentary Behaviour Guidelines for People Living with Chronic Conditions in Ireland consisted of multiple stages spanning August 2024 to February 2025. A multi-phased and mixed methods approach was employed to allow for the iterative development of the guidelines and messages. It included 5 stages: 1) Evidence review, 2) Drafting, 3) Consultation, 4) National stakeholder meeting, 5) Consolidation and refinement.

This section outlines the process applied to develop the physical activity and sedentary behaviour guidelines. Each stage combines a description of the methodology used and the corresponding outputs, where applicable.

Stage 1: Evidence Review

Phase 1 involved desk-top evidence reviews of the existing evidence and international physical activity guidelines for people living with a chronic condition. The objective of the evidence review was to inform the drafting of prototype Guidelines and Messages for consultation prior to stakeholder Consultation. Preparatory work in this included defining elements of the project scope (e.g. range of chronic conditions) and developing the search strategy and data extraction template.

Evidence Review Approach

In the preparation of this document, extensive purposive literature searches were carried out across key databases in addition to hand searches of relevant reference lists of key articles. Key literature on 'physical activity' OR 'exercise' AND existing key 'guidelines' OR 'recommendations' OR 'position papers' AND "chronic conditions", including searches with named chronic conditions were carried out. Articles included in the evidence review were existing international physical activity and sedentary behaviour guidelines, with particular focus to where existing guidelines made recommendations for people with chronic conditions. In addition, chronic conditions position papers, consensus statements and expert guidelines and salient review articles published since the most recent WHO physical activity guidelines (or prior where particularly relevant), were also considered for inclusion. In line with the aim of this project, literature that were focused on public and population health level were prioritised over explicitly 'clinical exercise prescription' guidelines.

A comparative analysis was then conducted across identified articles to identify consistencies or discrepancies and nuanced considerations with respect to WHO guidelines serving as a reference point (3,18,19). Finally, a review of an initial draft summary was conducted by the project team who have

expertise in physical activity and sedentary behaviour across a range of relevant chronic conditions. This ensured that the final inclusion material were appropriate, and that the findings were relevant. A narrative summary was conducted, identifying key evidence points for informing Draft Guidelines development.

Narrative Findings from the Evidence Review

Overview

The WHO produced updated physical activity and sedentary behaviour guidelines in 2020. Within these guidelines, chronic conditions of hypertension, cancer, and type 2 diabetes (T2D) were included within the frame of 'chronic conditions' (19). Other relevant conditions, including relevant neurodegenerative conditions (e.g. Multiple sclerosis and Parkinson's disease), and mental health disorders (e.g. schizophrenia and major depressive disorders) were framed under 'disability' within the WHO guidelines (18). The evidence summaries underpinning the guidelines and the guidelines themselves are described as preventative rather than therapeutic in nature, aimed at the role of physical activity and sedentary behaviour in preventing additional chronic conditions or worsening the existing conditions (19). Additional chronic conditions pertinent to the Irish context, such as cardiovascular disease, that extend the conceptualisation beyond hypertension, and key pulmonary and respiratory conditions were not well represented in these WHO guidelines. Concerns of broad condition representation in this regard have been previously raised in the literature (20).

With respect to understanding the inclusion of chronic conditions within contemporary public health level physical activity and sedentary behaviour guidelines, a recent scoping review and evidence synthesis offers a comprehensive overview from 28 countries (21). This review shows that only N=15 guidelines from the included 28 contexts refer to specific advice for people with chronic conditions of varying degrees: Austria, Finland, Germany, Kenya, Malaysia, Mexico, Norway, Pacific, Qatar, Singapore, Spain, Switzerland, UK, USA and the WHO guidelines. Of these fifteen, N=9 recommend that physical activity and sedentary behaviour guidelines for the general population remain the same for people with chronic conditions. A commonality across guidelines was that of 150-300 mins/week of aerobic physical activity or a minimum 75-150 mins/week of vigorous intensity aerobic physical activity with resistance exercise recommended twice per week, consistent with WHO physical activity guidelines. Other guidelines from Spain refer directly to recent WHO guidelines as a recommendation (21). Some guidelines, including Australia, Canada, China, Saudi Arabia, Uruguay, make an additional recommendation that those with chronic conditions should consult with a Health Care Practitioner (HCP) for more tailored guidance.

Notably, guidelines from the United States broadly resemble the WHO guidelines with respect to type, frequency and intensity of recommended physical activity, but offer general advice that people with chronic conditions should be under the care of a HCP, and may seek guidance from a HCP. Further to general guidelines, supplementary specific guidance is offered for people with osteoarthritis, T2D, hypertension and cancer within this work (22). Guidelines from Qatar specify explicit adapted physical activity guidelines for a number of specific conditions.

The aforementioned scoping review by Ranasinghe and colleagues makes clear a need for national physical activity and sedentary behaviour guidelines to include a focus on people with chronic conditions and disability to meet WHO Global Action Plan on Physical Activity (GAPPA) targets (21). Indeed, other contexts, such as Brazil, specify a clear need for more specific focus on chronic conditions populations within national physical activity and sedentary behaviour guidelines (23). Such national level guidelines are important for offering consensus of evidence, raising awareness on the benefits of physical activity in different groups, informing national level policy, underpinning regional monitoring efforts, and guiding national level research agendas (21). To this end, there is a need to develop specific National Physical Activity and Sedentary Behaviour Guidelines for Ireland with respect to appropriate inclusion of people with chronic conditions relevant to the Irish context.

The below section outlines recommendations from an evidence summary of key scholarly resources on physical activity and sedentary behaviour for people with chronic conditions. For the most part, people with chronic conditions typically engage in considerable amounts of self-management (24). Indeed, across conditions that are of a mild to moderate nature (where a person is living well with a chronic conditions), the evidence shows that the benefits of engaging in regular physical activity significantly outweigh any additional risk of adverse events occurring for people with chronic conditions (12). The findings presented below therefore summarise evidence relevant at a population level for people with chronic conditions in Ireland. These ought to be considered separate from clinical exercise recommendations. The findings from this evidence review offer overview general findings inclusive of all chronic conditions with respect to general recommendations, recommendations on intensity, frequency and duration, recommendations on type of activity, recommendations on sedentary behaviour, and recommendations on contraindications. This summary also includes a brief overview of the benefit of physical activity across relevant prominent conditions and key specific safety considerations relevant to the certain conditions that are not captured within general recommendations, which have been detailed in key position statements, and are nonetheless relevant at a public and population health level.

General Recommendations and Messaging Across All Chronic Conditions

Findings in this section pertain to the narrative summary of the evidence review. Initially presented are general recommendations that are designed to serve across all relevant chronic conditions. Considering both international physical activity and sedentary behaviour guidelines, and indeed recommendations relevant at a non-clinical level from important position statements and guidance documents, there was no convincing evidence identified that deviate in a significant way from the general recommendations outlined in WHO guidelines for people with chronic conditions and disability (18,19).

A general recommendation exists, that all adults, including those living with chronic conditions, should undertake regular physical activity. World Health Organisation guidelines indicate this to be a strong recommendation carrying moderate certainty evidence (18,19). This recommendation is also reflective of a broad range of position stands from leading authority organisations across chronic conditions included (25,26). World Health Organisation guidelines detail that persons with chronic conditions should try meet recommendations where possible, as able and without contraindication. Further 'good practice statements' offer a recommendation that, those who cannot attain the minimum guidelines should undertake moderate intensity physical activity to the maximum possible amount, which is also reflective of relevant position statements and National physical activity guidelines elsewhere (22,23). In this regard, there is a broad recommendation that adults with chronic conditions should start with small amounts of physical activity and increase frequency, intensity and duration over time, with the underpinning statement that "doing some physical activity is better than none". A notable exception regarding gradual increases in frequency, intensity and duration exists with respect to Parkinsons Diseases (PD) and Multiple Sclerosis (MS), which is addressed in the relevant section below.

Additional Practical Recommendations

World Health Organisation guidelines for people with chronic conditions and people with disabilities also recommend that pre-medical clearance is generally not necessary for individuals undertaking light and moderate physical activity (at intensity of brisk walking) that have no contraindication to exercise (18,19). However, ACSM guidelines recommend medical clearance in individuals previously inactive with existing CVD (27). An emphasis on commencement of light intensity physical activity is perhaps warranted here with respect to population level guidelines. Notwithstanding this, the recommendations from the WHO also assert that adults with chronic conditions may wish to consult with a HCP or equivalent qualified exercise specialist for advice on the types of physical activity appropriate for their needs, ability, function level, medications and overall treatment plan.

Intensity, Frequency and Duration of Activity

Intensity

Consistently, across guidelines, a strong recommendation with moderate certainty evidence supports the recommendation that moderate intensity physical activity is recommended where no contraindication is present. Again, where not contraindicated, guidelines also recommend that physical activity can also be accrued through vigorous intensity, which is also supported with a strong recommendation and moderate certainty evidence (18,19). Moreover, guidelines state that physical activity may be accrued through a combination of both moderate and vigorous intensity physical activity. In each of the above, there is a consistency of messaging across key position stands and consensus papers from chronic condition specific authority bodies (28–30).

Frequency and Duration

Global guidelines advocate that individuals with chronic conditions should accrue physical activity at a minimum weekly volume of 150-300 minutes in relation to moderate intensity aerobic physical activity. With respect to where vigorous physical activity is indicated (as above), it is recommended that 75-150 minutes are accrued weekly to achieve health benefit. This WHO guidelines indicate a strong recommendation with moderate certainty evidence surrounding this recommendation.

Guidelines also stipulate that adults with chronic conditions may increase the amount of moderate intensity aerobic physical activity to 300 minutes or greater with respect to moderate intensity, or indeed >150 minutes (vigorous intensity), or an equivalent combination throughout the week when not contraindicated by their medical condition. This evidence is presented as conditional based on the balance of benefits to harms and carries moderate certainty of evidence (18,19).

Types of Activity

The primary mode of activity detailed in WHO guidelines is aerobic physical activity. Further to aerobic physical activity, guidelines consistently advocate for the inclusion of resistance type exercise involving major muscle groups. In so doing, adults with chronic conditions are recommended to perform resistance exercise 2-3 times per week at moderate or greater intensity. This carries a strong recommendation with a moderate certainty evidence in WHO guidance (18,19). Among some guidance from authority bodies, 48 hours may be indicated between resistance exercise sessions to allow for muscle recovery, such as guidelines for exercise and physical activity from the Australian and New Zealand Society of Cardiac and Thoracic Surgeons (31). However, the weight of evidence to support this recommendation is unclear. In summary to this, a combination of aerobic and resistance-based physical activity is recommended for people with chronic conditions (18,19). Among some

people with certain conditions, resistance-based physical activity may require prioritisation over aerobic physical activity in contexts where a person is not capable of meeting physical activity guidelines. This is made clear within the relevant sections below.

Whilst the scope of the current evidence summary is not focused on older adults per se, there is a notable recommendation within WHO guidelines that older adults with chronic conditions, in addition to people with disability (that includes mental health conditions, PD and MS in the WHO guidelines) should do varied multicomponent physical activity that emphasises functional balance and strength training at moderate or greater intensity on 3 or more days a week to enhance functional capacity and prevent falls. This is a strong recommendation with a moderate certainty of evidence, and thus warrants consideration across chronic conditions populations for the current work. A prioritisation of functional fitness exercises is supported in other key position papers (26).

Interestingly, flexibility type exercise, as separate from 'balance and functional' exercise is not specifically well advocated for in WHO guidelines papers but is noted in key position papers on diabetes as important in protecting joint mobility, which may be negatively impacted by hyperglycaemia (26). This perhaps warrants more consideration in guideline development.

Sedentary Behaviour

National physical activity and sedentary behaviour guidelines reviewed as part of the prior mentioned scoping review (21), show that N=11 of included N=28 guidelines specify sedentary behaviour guidelines for people with disability specifically. Swiss guidelines make an additional recommendation to change sitting posture among people with limited walking and mobility related disability on top of general advice to minimise sitting where possible (32). The most comprehensive sedentary behaviour guidelines for people with chronic conditions specifically are found in the WHO guidelines (21). Only a small number of national level guidelines: Austria; Pacific Island Nations; Singapore; UK; USA make reference to guidelines on sedentary behaviour in the context of chronic conditions. These broadly and sometime to a lesser extent reflect WHO guidelines in that adults should limit the amount of time they spend in sedentary behaviour, avoiding prolonged periods of sedentary behaviour, and replacing sedentary time with physical activity of any intensity, including light intensity physical activity or incidental physical activity (21,22,33). World Health Organization guidelines offer an additional guideline for adults with chronic conditions in that they should strive to achieve more than the recommended levels of moderate to vigorous physical activity to mitigate deleterious health impacts of sedentary behaviour (18,19). The WHO Guidelines Development Group acknowledge the paucity of evidence underpinning the need to reduce sedentary behaviour in individuals with chronic conditions,

but are making this recommendation for chronic conditions based on the evidence that exists for the general population in the absence of evidence to the contrary (19).

Guidelines for Health Care and Exercise Professionals and Messaging

There is a broad perception of perceived risk of adverse outcomes of undertaking exercise with chronic conditions; there is a need for professionals to address this perception among people with chronic conditions and their support networks. It is recommended to start with small amounts of activity and increase frequency, intensity and duration over time, “doing some physical activity is better than none”, again, considerations of specific guidance in PD and MS are noted here. American College of Sport Medicine guidelines for physical activity and exercise in people with T2D, goes slightly further in their recommendation that, adults with comorbidity and older adults should strive for as much aerobic physical activity as their physical and mental health allows (26).

As already noted, WHO guidelines state that pre-exercise medical clearance is generally not necessary for individuals commencing light-moderate physical activity without contraindication to do physical activity (19). However, ACSM guidelines recommend medical clearance in individuals previously inactive with existing CVD (27). An emphasis on commencement of light intensity physical activity is perhaps warranted here, and clarity of messaging appears important.

Additional background work to this evidence review, where mapping of the special considerations presented in ACSM’s Guidelines for Exercise Testing and Prescription (11th edition, 2021) across multiple chronic diseases highlighted significant overlap that appear relevant here (34). Extended warm-up including gradual raising of heart rate and controlled movement of joints through full ‘range of motion’ is indicated, gradual and extended cool-down is indicated, initiation of a new exercise programme at a light-to-moderate intensity is indicated, short or intermittent duration activity at the outset may be indicated, using active recovery to increase the total volume of aerobic exercise that may be achieved may be advantageous, gradual progression based on exercise tolerance including “start low and go slow” is indicated, incorporating functional exercises that mirror activities of daily living may be advantageous, monitoring of symptoms is indicated, avoidance of the ‘Valsalva manoeuvre’ or activities that dramatically elevate blood pressure is indicated, considering the timing of exercise relative to medications and symptom burden may be advantageous (34). Rate of perceived exertion/breathlessness are relevant indicators of intensity/exertion instead of heart rate monitoring, as has been noted in key literature (35).

Contraindications for Physical Activity

Broadly, guidelines discussed here are intended at a population health level and thus are designed to be inclusive where possible. However, WHO guidelines are clear that people undergoing acute treatment phases of their condition or those not yet maintained on medication may get further advice from a HCP who can advise about specific clinical guidance (19). ACSM guidelines for exercise recommend medical clearance in individuals previously inactive with existing CVD (27). Additionally, review research regarding physical activity promotion in populations with chronic conditions broadly, assert that physical activity should be temporarily stopped until consultation with a HCP has occurred where symptom exacerbation occurs as a result of or during physical activity (12).

Condition Specific Recommendations

The below section is divided into sub sections that reflect some specific chronic conditions relevant to the Irish context and the proposed national physical activity and sedentary behaviour guidelines. In each, a broad rationale is offered that details the role of physical activity for the respective chronic condition and further condition specific recommendations, drawn from key position papers and guidance documents, that are not included in general recommendations.

Post Cancer Treatment

There is a robust body of evidence that physical activity is beneficial for health and wellbeing in individuals following treatment for cancer (36,37). Guidelines in this space are specifically focused on the role of physical activity to maintain or improve physical functioning, improve psychosocial outcomes, improve quality of life, reduce associated fatigue and reduce risk surrounding comorbidity (38). There is now broad acknowledgment that physical activity is beneficial for the health, wellbeing and quality of life in individuals following treatment for a range of differing cancer diagnoses (30,39). Recommendations here are directed at persons in the 'post treatment' phase of the cancer journey, which is as separate from pre or active treatment (39).

Post Cancer Special Considerations for Safety

Physical activity for people following cancer treatment should be undertaken with the recognition that progressive overload may need to be applied gradually in persons with significant deconditioning. Among some individuals, a tailored approach to individuals' abilities, where specific adaptation may be required based on treatment related contraindications and/or anticipated trajectory of cancer and/or health status can be necessary (22,28). Notable concerns that may warrant consultation with suitably qualified exercise practitioners or HCP to inform safe physical activity prescription include, bone metastases, lymphedema, reduced range of motion, chronic pain (40), persistent and significant

fatigue, anticoagulant therapy (36). Such practitioners may also be able to advise about site specific activation or loading of areas of the body that may be impacted from cancer or treatment (36,39,41).

In people post-cancer treatment, a number of other symptoms and experiences may be relevant and require nuanced consideration in physical activity planning. For instance, thrombocytopenia: physical activity that carries risk of fall and blunt force trauma through activity, such as contact sport, carry a recommendation to be avoided where possible (36). Neutropenia: Robust hygiene practices are recommended in physical activity planning, including handwashing, hygiene practices surrounding exercise equipment, and considerations of exercise with other people who may be unwell. High intensity physical activity during neutropenic periods is also not advisable, as this may negatively impact white blood cell count and function (36). Cachexia: An emphasis on resistance exercise to stimulate hypertrophy may be indicated. Individuals with cachexia should be assisted to consider their 'goals', as cachexia may reflect disease progression in some. Sarcopenia: An emphasis on resistance exercise to stimulate hypertrophy may be indicated. Consider that aerobic physical activity may impact on muscle accrual, thus physical activity planning may need to be adjusted to reflect this balance. Bone loss: An emphasis on resistance exercise to stimulate hypertrophy and impact loading may be indicated. Activity to stimulate balance is also advisable. Consider moderate- high intensity resistance exercise prior to initiating exercise with impact loading (36). Fatigue: Low intensity physical activity can be effective at reducing fatigue and may be indicated to avoid 'rebound fatigue'. Short bouts of high intensity aerobic and resistance exercise should be considered in those that can tolerate such intensities. Reduced muscle mass may indicate a need for emphasis on resistance exercise over aerobic exercise in physical activity planning. Avoid 'total rest' or long periods of no exercise (36). At risk of Lymphoedema: Compression garments may be appropriate except where they serve as a barrier to physical activity. Aquatic based physical activity can offer compression effects (36). Urinary incontinence: The inclusion of pelvic floor, kegel and resistance exercise for large muscle groups of the pelvis, abdomen and spine are generally indicated (40,42). High impact physical activity may not be indicated in this cohort. Hydration and toilet facility ought to be considered in planning physical activity. Peripheral neuropathy: Low impact physical activity may reduce pain experienced during physical activity. Balance and proprioception activation within activity are indicated (36).

Cardiovascular Disease and Hypertension

There is extensive evidence to support a role for physical activity in improving cardiovascular health among people with CVD, including reducing chronic elevated blood pressure and improving blood lipid profiles among at risk groups (25). Hypertension is a major risk factor in cardiovascular disease and coronary events (43)). Aerobic and dynamic resistance physical activity is widely understood to have

antihypertensive effects for individuals with hypertension and individuals in sub-hypertensive states at risk of hypertension (44,45). To this end, regular physical inactivity is also implicated in the progression of hypertension to adverse cardiac events and stroke (46). Indeed, national physical activity guidelines from the United States note that increased physical activity levels may necessitate adjustment in hypertensive medication in consultation with relevant HCP (22). However, a small proportion of the population will be non-responders or adverse responders with respect to blood pressure following physical activity (25). In the management of cardiovascular disease and hypertension, a combination of aerobic and resistance based physical activity, in addition to increased levels of incidental physical activity, with simultaneous concerted effort to reduce sedentary behaviour is advocated for by the International Society of Hypertension (47).

Cardiovascular and Hypertension Special Considerations for Safety

Resistance exercise among those with hypertension should not begin at high intensity. Physical activity bouts have an acute effect on blood pressure. Breath holding is not advisable in resistance exercise training where high blood pressure is indicated (48). Pharmacological intervention can lead to rapid blood pressure reduction post exercise, therefore physical activity sessions should be terminated using a graded reduction of intensity, or 'cool down' phase (27,48).

Diabetes

Physical activity is widely acknowledged to have a role in glycaemic management among people with T2 diabetes. There is good evidence, in particular, for regular aerobic physical activity to reduce time spent in hyperglycaemia (26,49,50). Evidence is also supportive of the role of physical activity in promoting broader physical health and functioning outcomes in people with diabetes who are at risk of broader chronic cardio metabolic health problems and diabetes related complications. Both aerobic and resistance exercise are advocated for within current recommendations, though it is acknowledged that both modes used in combination appears optimal in reaching on improved blood glucose profiles (26).

Diabetes Special Considerations for Safety

Checking of blood glucose levels before, during and post exercise may be advisable. Physical activity and exercise should be conducted with someone or persons should be notified about physical activity where there is a potential for hypoglycaemia event. Physical activity should be avoided for 24 hours following severe hypoglycaemia event. Postprandial physical activity is advocated for among people with T2D (49). Individuals taking insulin may have problematic experiences with high intensity exercise, and further advice may be here indicated (26). Among those with existing hyperglycaemia,

consensus recommendations state that if blood glucose is >300 mg/dL-1 (16.7 mmol/L-1), caution should be advised when exercising and further advice from a HCP appears indicated (26). Appropriate and comfortable footwear selection may be pertinent among some individuals (22). Consideration of clothing and the environment is also warranted in the context of those who may have thermoregulation inhibition.

Mental Health Conditions

People with widely prevalent mental health conditions (such as anxiety disorders, depressive disorders and psychosis) (51), can attain multidimensional benefits from undertaking regular physical activity or structured exercise (52,53). Physical activity can have favourable effects on key mental health symptoms, such as improved mood states, reduced symptoms of anxiety and improved cognitive function, in addition to favourable global functioning, physical health and social outcomes relevant to people with mental health conditions (52,54–56). Physical activity should be recognised as a mental health therapeutic, and thus recommended in this context, in addition to being a support to physical health promotion (57). Modest weight loss expectations through physical activity/exercise should be made clear when discussing physical activity in this context, particularly where psychotropic medication that carry unfavourable cardiometabolic side-effects are implicated (57). There is a need to acknowledge specific barriers to physical activity related to mental health symptoms, in addition to usually reported physical activity barriers in the context of physical activity promotion (29,56). Autonomously directed physical activity, usually within domains of leisure and transport, are therefore perceived as optimal (58). Mentally passive sedentary behaviour is particularly unfavourable in populations with mental health conditions (59). There are no specific safety considerations beyond that of the general recommendations already outlined.

Pulmonary-related Conditions

While acknowledging the often inherent reduced capacity for exercise in some pulmonary conditions like Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD), exercise has been shown to have beneficial impact on a number of key health outcomes. For instance, exercise may improve aerobic capacity, reduce symptoms of dyspnoea, improve fatigue and quality of life outcomes (60). Physical activity is also now implicated in anti-inflammatory responses and dyspnoea perception in people with asthma (61). Recent expert guidance on physical activity for people with chronic respiratory diseases has further recommended a consideration for resistance exercise to include muscles of the chest and back (62).

Pulmonary-related Conditions Special Considerations for Safety

Exertional breathlessness is commonplace among people with respiratory conditions. Shorter bouts of physical activity (e.g. 10–15) minutes may be appropriate among some conditions (62). All physical activity intensity should be dependent on dyspnoea experienced (35).

Multiple Sclerosis and Parkinson Disease

Multiple sclerosis (MS) and Parkinson disease (PD) are chronic conditions impacting the central nervous system with typical disability and mobility implications. Evidence shows the physical activity can play an important role in improving and maintaining physical functioning (e.g. aerobic capacity, gait, balance), mental health related symptoms and quality of life in people with MS (63) and PD (64,65). In this context, it is noteworthy that physical activity recommendations from recent consensus work advocate for the incorporation of daily individualised flexibility type physical activity, in addition to neuromotor stimulating physical activity 3–6 times/week targeting fall prevention, postural stability, coordination, and agility at various levels of challenge (seated, standing, walking, and upper limb). In this way, multicomponent physical activity and aquatic physical activity may be relevant (66) General guidelines above pertain to mild-moderate MS and mild–moderate PD with respect to symptoms experiences and functioning.

Multiple Sclerosis and Parkinson Disease Special Considerations for Safety

People with MS are advised to initiate 10-minute bouts of physical activity initially and to increase gradually to sessions of 30 minutes or greater. In MS and PD, progression in exercise is advised through duration and frequency initially, and then then lastly through intensity. Environmental, clothing and hydration may be important considerations for initiating physical activity in people with MS where heat sensitivity may be implicated in their condition (67). Visual and auditory cues that promote movement coordination may be indicated among some people with MS and PD (67). The mode of aerobic exercise may be pertinent with respect to safety. Some people with PD experience freezing of gait and other risks of falls, and thus walking and running may be contraindicated among some individuals who are of particular risk of falling in certain contexts. Exercise during medication cycles in an 'on' state appear to carry reduced risk of adverse events and should be considered in preparation for physical activity (64,67).

Overweight and Obesity

The relationship between energy expenditure (e.g. through physical activity), energy intake, excess weight and adiposity is complex. That said, physical activity is recognised as one approach within a recommended multidimensional approach to weight management among people living with

overweight and obesity (68,69). In this regard, physical activity may have a modest role in weight loss, and weight loss maintenance among people with obesity (69). Notwithstanding this, physical activity is important in the context of cardiometabolic risk reduction, insulin sensitivity, and improved cardiorespiratory fitness among people living with overweight or obesity. To this end, regular physical activity is important for overall health and quality of life enhancement among people living with obesity (70). Physical activity is also important for the preservation of lean body mass in the context of weight-loss efforts, and is thus an important health consideration for the management of this chronic condition. Volume of physical activity is important in the context of weight-loss, where small volumes of physical activity are unlikely to lead to weight loss (68,70). There is some evidence that >200 or indeed >300 minutes aerobic MVPA (60 mins on most days) may be desirable for weight-loss. Notwithstanding this, modest weight loss expectations (estimated 2-3 kg) through physical activity/exercise should be understood in context by relevant populations (69). Physical activity initiation is therefore advised under the broader guise of holistic health promotion, rather than weight loss (68,70).

Overweight and Obesity Special Considerations for Safety

Persons taking pharmacological therapy for obesity or who have undergone bariatric surgery should consider personal capacity and abilities, and may require medical clearance where medical status indicates (68).

Stage 2: Drafting (Team Review and Drafting)

A project team (listed on page 2) with relevant expertise across specific chronic conditions was established to oversee the development of the chronic conditions guidelines to ensure credibility, relevance and practicality. The project team were engaged throughout the development process and played a key role in reviewing and interpreting the available evidence. Early in the process, they were invited to recommend additional relevant literature and to help contextualise international findings within the Irish health system. Panel members were also consulted during the development of the Evidence review, providing iterative feedback, ensuring a collaborative effort on the development of evidence-informed Guidelines and Messaging. Following this, the completed Evidence review was provided to the project team, with an accompanying initial draft of the Guidelines and Messages. The group were given time to review and consider this information and subsequent meetings. The group Chair facilitated discussion on both the Evidence review and Draft Guidelines and Messages, and feedback was noted. Following the meeting, the group were asked to provide further input remotely. The feedback was used to refine the initial drafts to produce drafts for wider stakeholder consultation (see Stage 3). The project team insights were used in refining the Draft Guidelines ahead of wider stakeholder consultation. Their feedback helped shape the tone, structure, and content of subsequent drafts, ensuring that they were both scientifically robust and responsive to the needs and contexts of people with chronic conditions. The output of Stage 2 was Draft Guidelines, Draft Good Practice Statements and Messages for people with chronic conditions. These draft materials were subsequently used to prompt inquiry during the subsequent Stage 3. Detailed below. Specifically, the drafts included:

- i. An introduction outlining the scope of the guidelines and a brief evidence summary of the benefits of physical activity and risk of sedentary behaviour in the population
- ii. The physical activity and sedentary behaviour Guidelines
- iii. Good practice statements
- iv. Specific population considerations
- v. Messages for users
- vi. Messages for health and social care professionals
- vii. Messages for physical activity professionals

Stage 3: Stakeholder Consultation

The Draft Guidelines and Messages were disseminated for stakeholder consultation in the form of an anonymous online survey. The stakeholder population of interest were end users (people living with chronic conditions), professionals and practitioners working with end-users (from both the health and physical activity sector) and others (i.e. academics, professionals within support structures advocacy and representative bodies, policymakers). End users were defined as adults with a diagnosed long-term health condition requiring ongoing medical attention or limiting activities of daily living or both (24).

Stakeholders were recruited through the online dissemination of the study information and survey (See Appendix 3 and 4 for Recruitment advertisement). The HSE acted as a dissemination partner and disseminated the study information through email, website and social media channels. The information was disseminated through SETU online platforms and through the networks of the project team. Other gatekeepers such as representative bodies, e.g. patient charities, support groups, were asked to share the information through their communication channels.

The survey was administered via the Qualtrics platform. The surveys for people living with chronic conditions presented only the relevant Draft Messages through both open and closed questions that collected data on perceptions of the level of practicality, clarity and informativeness of the Draft Messages. The survey for professionals and practitioners were presented with the relevant Draft Guidelines, Good Practice Statements, Specific Population Considerations and Messages for professionals. These surveys collected data through both open and closed questions on participants' perceptions of acceptability. The domains of acceptability assessed included, clarity, relevance, appropriateness, and perceived effectiveness. Quantitative data was analysed using descriptive statistical analysis and qualitative data using a descriptive approach to thematic analysis (71,72). Responses were analysed to determine levels of agreement with key elements of the guidelines and to identify recurring themes across stakeholder groups.

Approval to conduct anonymous online surveys during stakeholder consultation were approved by the Research Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Health Sciences, South East Technological University (SETU/HSREC/24/25/004).

Stakeholder Consultation Findings (End Users)

Demographic Characteristics

The sample included N=706 individuals living with chronic conditions. From this N=198 (32%) were male and N=420 (67%) were female. Among respondents, 89% of the sample listed their ethnicity as 'white/Irish', with the remaining 0.2% (Black/Irish), 0.2% (other), and 10% (not disclosed). The majority of the sample were above the age of 60 years, as per the below Table 1. Data were gathered from respondents across 24 counties in Ireland, however thirteen of these accounted for minimal data (<1.3% of the sample). A breakdown of counties where the majority of data were collected, alongside salient demographic information is shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Demographic characteristics of end-user survey respondents

Demographic characteristic area	N (%)
Dominant Geographical Locations	
<i>Dublin</i>	381 (61)
<i>Kildare</i>	41 (6.6)
<i>Wicklow</i>	30 (5)
<i>Laois</i>	24 (4)
<i>Cork</i>	22 (4)
<i>Galway</i>	
Age	
<i>25 – 29 years</i>	4 (.5)
<i>30-39 years</i>	12 (2)
<i>40-49 years</i>	26 (4)
<i>50 – 59 years</i>	61 (9)
<i>60-69 years</i>	192 (28)
<i>70-79 years</i>	279 (40)
<i>>80 years</i>	50 (7)
Education	
<i>Lower secondary</i>	60 (9)
<i>Upper secondary</i>	130 (19)
<i>Technical/Vocational</i>	54 (8)
<i>Advanced Cert./Apprenticeship</i>	53 (8)
<i>Bachelor's Degree</i>	164 (23)
<i>Postgraduate</i>	120 (17)
<i>PhD or higher</i>	7 (1)
Employment Status	
<i>Retired from employment</i>	423 (61)
<i>Working for payment/profit</i>	77 (11)
<i>Short-term unemployed</i>	3 (.4)
<i>Long-term unemployed</i>	3 (.4)

<i>Student</i>	4 (.5)
<i>Looking after home/family</i>	29 (4)
<i>Unable to work due to sickness</i>	58 (8)
<i>Other</i>	24 (3)
Reported Health Status	
<i>Very good</i>	48 (7)
<i>Good</i>	276 (40)
<i>Fair</i>	231 (33)
<i>Bad</i>	61 (9)
<i>Very bad</i>	10 (1)

Acceptability of Draft Messages for People with Chronic Conditions

In addition to being asked about clarity, usefulness in providing information, and practicality of each individual draft message, respondents to the survey for end users with chronic conditions were also asked to consider the Draft Messages as a whole in relation to a few key areas. The findings here illustrate that a majority of respondents (56%) agreed that the prototype Draft Messages were ‘appealing’, would motivate them to be physically active (50%), allowed them to feel supported (52%), would find them helpful (55%), and that they would recommend them to other people with chronic conditions (54%). A further breakdown of the agreement with these areas, viewing the Draft Messages as a whole, is shown below in Table 2. A breakdown of agreement data with respect to clarity, usefulness of providing information and practicality across each of the respective Draft Messages areas is shown in the later Table 3. See Appendix 1 for Draft Guidelines and Messages presented at this stage and Appendix 2 for link to final document.

Table 2. Acceptability of the draft messages (as a whole) for end users with chronic conditions

‘Draft’ Messages to end users with chronic conditions (as a whole)	Strongly disagree N (%)	Somewhat disagree N (%)	Neither agree/disagree N (%)	Somewhat agree N (%)	Strongly agree N (%)
The guidelines/ messages are appealing to me	41 (6)	12 (2)	42 (6)	197 (28)	197 (28)
Guidelines/Messages motivate me to be physically active	34	15 (2)	70 (10)	185 (26)	170 (24)
Guideline/ Messages help me to feel supported	38 (5)	18 (3)	61 (9)	183 (26)	181 (26)
Overall, I find them helpful	39 (5)	14 (2)	36 (5)	184 (26)	207 (29)
I would recommend these guidelines to other people with chronic conditions	43 (6)	15 (2)	38 (5)	172 (24)	209 (30)

Qualitative Feedback from End Users on Draft Messages

In addition to quantitative data gathered by the end user survey, open response options were provided to gather qualitative data regarding the Draft Messages as a whole. Descriptive thematic analysis identified four overarching, and yet connected theme issues relevant to the Draft Messages to help inform future iterative message refinement for future stages of development. The overarching themes identified in the qualitative data were:

- The importance of clarity, simplicity and practicality;
- The importance of motivation and encouragement;
- Desired personalisation and specificity;
- The importance of accessibility, inclusivity for all different chronic conditions

The importance of clarity, simplicity and practicality

Many of the qualitative comments noted a need for the guideline messages to be simple in their wording, so as not to overcomplicate the message ethos.

“Make the guidelines simple to understand... Do not complicate with loads of figures and science language.”

Qualitative responses here also included advice for the developing project team to be aware of practical barriers that many ‘target populations’ may face, and thus future refinement should seek to offer practical advice to help people overcome these barriers.

“Many elderly won’t know what resistance training/bands are.”

The importance of accessibility, inclusivity for all different chronic conditions

This theme undoubtedly intersects with the previously outlined theme, but extends the meaning to that of content within the message guidelines, being inclusive of all persons living with chronic conditions.

“A feeling of help and support are available and that it's easily accessible are important. Plus feeling that you're not so alone”.

Indeed, it was acknowledged that ‘chronic conditions’ is a broad term within which there is the potential for considerable heterogeneity across different domains. Respondents voiced concern that the Draft Guideline Messages would offer relevance across multiple conditions and levels of physical ability.

“I think that if you were to issue guidelines for exercise for chronic issues you have to keep that in mind that there are many people who live very full lives and who are not much impacted by a chronic diagnosis whereas there are many others who cannot work, study or indeed leave the house most days. A chronic diagnosis exists on a spectrum and therefore capacities for exercise are the same”.

Desired personalisation and specificity

Some respondents commented that they desired guidelines messages that would be specific to individual conditions, so as to account for nuanced condition specific experiences relevant to physical activity. Many of the respondents shared experiences of overcoming barriers specific to their condition or ideas they feel are important for staying physically active in the context of their experiences of their conditions.

“I walk every day and since I had a Stent procedure almost 2 years ago, have been doing various other physical exercises also, and feel it's all wonderful for physical and mental health. Everyone should be encouraged to do some form of exercise each day.”

Participants sought specificity with regard to safety, with many expressing desire for reassurance within the guidelines messages that physical activity is safe for them to do. This appeared in a number of ways.

“More reassurance that moderate to high intensity exercise won't exacerbate pre-existing pain”

“Many people living with chronic conditions are scared to exercise. We need a lot of encouragement and support, as well as information.”

“Patient with a chronic condition needs more personal guidance on exercise, not just general advice. e.g. COPD patient will have breathing issues, and general advice is not informative.”

While further detailed in the below theme, other respondents offered insight that ‘too high a bar’, could have a deleterious effect on the individuals symptoms, particularly among persons with conditions who are not a regular exercisers.

“For some conditions exercise can render fatigue worse and pacing is so important, I have discovered that some individuals can be made feel worse if they attempt exercise and are then set back.”

The importance of motivation and encouragement

Respondents of the survey expressed opinion that guidelines messages ought to have motivation and positivity at their core, rather than being framed in a way that is punitive or placing undue emphasis on negative consequences of inactivity.

"Exercise needs to be promoted but in a positive and enjoyable way."

"You get a better response if people feel encouraged to do something rather than it being expressed as a pure fact"

Related to, and indeed intersecting with the theme of 'The importance of accessibility and inclusion', were the concerns voiced that messages must not be de-motivating through explicit physical activity level targets that could be perceived as unattainable by many.

"There is often a lot of pressure from people to exercise when you are sick and it can be made out to be like you are lazy or not trying hard enough. I would just be worried that one of the statements regarding aerobic exercise and the length of time recommended would make people feel guilty when they are physically unable to do that much."

Table 3. Agreement with clarity, Informativeness and practicality of draft messages for end users

'Draft' Messages to end users with chronic conditions	Strongly disagree N(%)	Somewhat disagree N(%)	Neither agree nor disagree N(%)	Somewh at agree N(%)	Strongly agree N(%)
Guideline message 1. General message regarding the benefit of physical activity across chronic conditions.					
Message was clear and easy to understand	30 (4)	6 (0.8)	19 (3)	59 (8)	417 (60)
Message was informative	17 (2.4)	15 (2)	20 (3)	97 (14)	345 (50)
Message was practical	11 (1.5)	15 (2)	21 (3)	83 (12)	312 (45)
Guideline message 2: Message recommendation for both muscle strengthening and aerobic activity					
Message was clear and easy to understand	20 (3)	6 (0.8)	13 (2)	95 (14)	400 (60)
Message was informative	15 (2)	7 (1)	28 (4)	104 (15)	315 (45)
Message was practical	7 (1)	13 (2)	25 (4)	106 (15)	299 (43)
Guideline Message 3. Message regarding recommended volume and intensity of activity					
Message was clear and easy to understand	24 (3)	44 (6)	36 (5)	155 (22)	268 (39)
Message was informative	9 (1)	32 (5)	39 (6)	123 (17)	254 (37)
Message was practical	10 (1.4)	43 (6)	37 (5)	127 (18)	221 (32)
Guideline Message 4. Message on achieving recommended muscle strengthening recommendations					
Message was clear and easy to understand	8 (1)	34	35 (5)	131 (19)	237 (34)
Message was informative	8 (1)	24	29 (4)	124 (18)	274 (39)
Message was practical	12 (2)	22 (3)	31 (4)	153 (21)	311 (44)
Guideline Message 5. Message on value of small amounts of physical activity.					
Message was clear and easy to understand	17 (2)	7	6	67 (10)	433 (61)
Message was informative	14	7	11	68 (10)	360 (51)
Message was practical	9	13	17 (2)	67 (9)	346 (49)
Guideline Message 6. Message regarding self-monitoring of activity intensity and progression					

'Draft' Messages to end users with chronic conditions	Strongly disagree N(%)	Somewhat disagree N(%)	Neither agree nor disagree N(%)	Somewhat agree N(%)	Strongly agree N(%)
Message was clear and easy to understand	13	19	26 (4)	135 (19)	335 (47)
Message was informative	11	15	21	110 (16)	300 (42)
Message was practical	10	16	25 (4)	113 (16)	281 (40)
Guideline Message 7. Message on medical clearance.					
Message was clear and easy to understand	30 (4)	6	19 (3)	60 (9)	420 (60)
Message was informative	17 (2)	15 (2)	20 (3)	98 (14)	348 (49)
Message was practical	11	15	22 (3)	83 (12)	314 (45)
Guideline Message 8. Message about progression of physical activity.					
Message was clear and easy to understand	12 (2)	13	17	109 (15)	379 (54)
Message was informative	6	8	22	107 (15)	317 (45)
Message was practical	5	14	26	98 (14)	305 (43)
Guideline Message 9. Message about contraindications to activity.					
Message was clear and easy to understand	18 (3)	5	4	38 (5)	462 (66)
Message was informative	10	4	12	47 (7)	383 (54)
Message was practical	10	5	10 (1)	39 (6)	390 (55)
Guideline Message 10. Message about health warning signs.					
Message was clear and easy to understand	8 (1)	1	4	45 (6)	465 (66)
Message was informative	4 (<1)	0	11	46 (7)	386 (55)
Message was practical	5 (<1)	1	11	41 (6)	390 (55)
Guideline Message 11. Message about choosing enjoyable activity.					
Message was clear and easy to understand	9 (1)	7 (<1)	8	78 (11)	427 (61)
Message was informative	7 (<1)	7 (<1)	12	71 (10)	364 (52)
Message was practical	7 (<1)	7 (<1)	16 (2)	70 (10)	350 (50)
Guideline Message 12. Message about limiting prolonged sedentary time.					
Message was clear and easy to understand	9 (1)	4 (<1)	10	50 (7)	456 (65)
Message was informative	7 (<1)	3 (<1)	18 (3)	54 (8)	377 (53)
Message was practical	6 (<1)	5 (<1)	18 (3)	58 (8)	369 (52)

Appendix 1 provides the full Draft Messages used during this consultation. Appendix 2 provides a link to the finalised Messages (Knowledge, Perceptions and Motivation) as part of the overall physical activity and sedentary behaviour guidelines published for people living well with chronic conditions.

Stakeholder Consultation (Health, Social Care, Physical Activity and Sports Professionals)

Health and social care professionals were also invited to provide insights on the Draft Guidelines during Stage 3. While the target population were presented with the Messages to translate the guidelines, professionals were presented with a Draft of the Guidelines that included: Guidelines, Good Practice Statements, Specific Population Considerations, and Messages for Professionals.

Demographic Characteristics

Total sample of professional N=117, with the majority being female (>80%) participated in the survey. Over 60% of these worked in the Health Sector, 24% worked in physical activity provision, 5% in academia, and 9% 'other' (e.g. Advocacy). The majority reported that they promote physical activity to a large extent or very large extent within their professional remit.

Agreement on Clarity and Appropriateness of Draft Guidelines

Professional stakeholder respondents were presented with all prototype Draft Physical Activity and Sedentary Behaviour Guidelines for People with Chronic Conditions. Respondents were requested to rate the clarity and appropriateness of Guidelines overall, and as with the target population survey, to offer qualitative comments to support and contextualise their response. Respondents were also invited to rate the appropriateness of each Good Practice Statement as well as each statement for Specific population consideration. Qualitative data to contextualise and support findings were again gathered here. Lastly, respondents rated the Draft Messages for professionals in relation to relevance, feasibility, support in delivering information, overall helpfulness and how likely they were to use them in practice, again with room for qualitative comment provided.

In relation to the Draft Guidelines, the majority of respondents indicated good agreement in the Clarity and Appropriateness of the prototype Draft Guidelines. See Table 4 below. More nuanced qualitative feedback in relation to the Guidelines follows this.

Table 4. Overall agreement with clarity and appropriateness of prototype draft guidelines

'Draft' Physical activity and sedentary behaviour guidelines for chronic conditions	Strongly disagree N(%)	Somewhat disagree N(%)	Neither agree nor disagree N(%)	Somewh at agree N(%)	Strongly agree N(%)
Draft Guidelines perceived to be clear and easy to understand	7 (6)	7 (6)	0	34 (29)	43 (37)
Draft Guideline are appropriate	8 (7)	9 (8)	3 (2.5)	30 (26)	40 (34)

Qualitative Feedback on Draft Guidelines

While participants engaged in qualitative analysis prior to reviewing the Draft Good Practice Statements, descriptive thematic analysis of the qualitative data gathered key feedback from professional stakeholder respondents. From N=42 professional stakeholders that provided qualitative feedback, qualitative sentiment were organised into four overarching themes, with sub-theme issues

within each of these four themes. These themes were 1. 'Being realistic, and setting achievable targets', 2. 'The importance of accessible and inclusivity', 3. 'Providing specific information, including safety for chronic conditions', and 4. 'The importance of emphasis on other activity components beyond aerobic'. This qualitative feedback helped inform further refinement of the Guidelines prior to Stage 4. A more in-depth account of qualitative findings from professional stakeholder respondents surrounding the Draft Guidelines is found in Table 5 below. The final published guidelines can be found in Appendix 2.

Table 5. Summarised qualitative feedback on draft guidelines from professionals

Theme	Sub theme	Quote example
T1. Being realistic, and setting achievable targets	ST1A. Draft guidelines might be too ambitious for some (at certain times). There is need for more attainable/graded guidelines. Unachievable guidelines may be harmful.	<p><i>"I think the guidelines are good, however I think the public need support in how to set targets, gentle progression and a health professionals input to give them confidence to implement and progress"</i></p> <p><i>"As these guidelines are for people with chronic illnesses, I think it's important to have some wording that accounts for times when they may not be well due to their illness and exercise is more difficult. So maybe include a recommendation to incorporate even some light intensity physical activity when feeling particularly unwell as any movement is better than none."</i></p>
	ST1 B. Desired consistency and clarity of defined activity durations.	<i>"I'd rather that the guidelines state 150 minutes - 300 minutes of moderate intensity activity or 75 - 150 minutes higher intensity activity. Think it's an easier message to get across to the public. Some people accumulate bouts of activity i.e 10 minute bouts."</i>
T2. The importance of accessible and inclusivity	ST2 A. The importance of using layman's terms/visuals and ensuring the guidelines are accessible to people with low literacy levels.	<i>"I would come up with a very clear visual representation of the recommended PA required again across a day or a week to support clearer understanding, communication and facilitation of individuals to apply the guidelines in their everyday lives."</i>
	ST2 B. Examples of activities and clear explanations of scientific terms (e.g. "moderate", "vigorous", "sedentary") were recommended.	<p><i>"I think there needs to be clear everyday definitions and examples of what is meant by moderate and vigorous physical activity to be clearer."</i></p> <p><i>"Need to clarify what is sedentary."</i></p>

T3. 'Providing specific information, including safety for chronic conditions'	ST3 A. The guidelines need to acknowledge flux state of wellness among people with chronic conditions. Acknowledge adapted activity role.	<i>"There are very few within the population of older adults with chronic respiratory conditions who would achieve true vigorous activity - clarity as to how vigorous is "vigorous" for this population is important, as they can find even moderate intensity exercise very challenging/perceived as more difficult due to shortness of breath versus actual increase in heart rate etc."</i>
	ST3 B. A need for some balance activity recommended in draft guidelines.	
	ST3 C. The need for guidelines to ensure safe exercise practices for individuals with specific chronic conditions.	<i>"There should be some consideration for the type of chronic condition, some guidance to ensure the exercise is safe and beneficial for them to undertake"</i> <i>"A note should also be included to address accessibility to highlight that some people with chronic disease will need modifications and support to engage in such levels of PA each week"</i>
	ST3 D. It should be highlighted that physical activity is beneficial for people with chronic conditions.	<i>"Badly needed!"</i>
	ST3 E. The importance of graded activity, including warm-up/cool-down.	<i>"Should also include the importance of a warm up and cool down especially for those with chronic conditions."</i>
	ST3 F. Information on risk required.	<i>"Have additional advise when periods of worsening symptoms occur."</i>
T4. The importance of emphasis on activity components beyond 'aerobic'.	ST4 A. Strength training ought to appear a higher in order to infer a level of importance.	<i>"Strength training x2 weekly is the most important message to get across in my opinion."</i>
	ST4 B. Balance for older persons with chronic conditions requires emphasis.	<i>"Older adults should be made more aware of balance training and the importance of it."</i>

Professional Respondents Rating of Appropriateness of Chronic Conditions Good Practice Statements

Respondents were asked to rate the perceived levels of appropriateness for each of the eleven Draft Good Practice Statements. The majority of responses across all Good Practice Statements were positive, with most respondents rating the statements as either appropriate or strongly appropriate, indicating high levels of perceived appropriateness overall. A detailed breakdown of appropriateness responses for each Good Practice Statement area are shown below in Table 6. The Draft Good Practices Statements used during this stage can be found in Appendix 1.

Table 6. Professional respondents rating of appropriateness of draft good practice statements

Good Practice Statement	Appropriateness Rating N (%)
1 Modification to 'ability' Statement	Strongly inappropriate: 2 (1.7) Inappropriate: 1 Neither appropriate nor inappropriate: 4 (3) Appropriate: 30 (26) Strongly appropriate: 45 (38)
2 Progression of activity Statement	Strongly inappropriate: 2 (1.7) Inappropriate: 1 Neither appropriate nor inappropriate: 0 Appropriate: 27 (23) Strongly appropriate: 52 (44)
3 Mode of activity Statement	Strongly inappropriate: 2 (1.7) Inappropriate: 0 Neither appropriate nor inappropriate: 1 Appropriate: 21 (18) Strongly appropriate: 58 (50)
4 Gauging intensity Statement	Strongly inappropriate: 2 (1.7) Inappropriate: 0 Neither appropriate nor inappropriate: 6 (5) Appropriate: 29 (25) Strongly appropriate: 45 (39)
5 Professional advice Statement	Strongly inappropriate: 2 (1.7) Inappropriate: 3 (2.5) Neither appropriate nor inappropriate: 1 Appropriate: 34 (29) Strongly appropriate: 42 (36)
6 Medical clearance Statement	Strongly inappropriate: 5(4) Inappropriate: 11 (9) Neither appropriate nor inappropriate: 13 (11) Appropriate: 32 (27) Strongly appropriate: 21 (18)
7 Warning signs Statement	Strongly inappropriate: 2 (1.7) Inappropriate: 1 Neither appropriate nor inappropriate: 3 (2.5) Appropriate: 19 (16) Strongly appropriate: 57 (49)
8 Condition contraindications Statement	Strongly inappropriate: 2 (1.7) Inappropriate: 1 Neither appropriate nor inappropriate: 1 Appropriate: 27 (23) Strongly appropriate: 50 (43)

9 Symptoms exacerbation Statement	Strongly inappropriate: 2 (1.7) Inappropriate: 1 Neither appropriate nor inappropriate: 0 Appropriate: 25 (21) Strongly appropriate: 54 (46)
10 Environmental conditions Statement	Strongly inappropriate: 2 (1.7) Inappropriate: 2 (1.7) Neither appropriate nor inappropriate: 10 (9) Appropriate: 28 (24) Strongly appropriate: 39 (33)
11 Sedentary behaviour Statement	Strongly inappropriate: 7(6) Inappropriate: 18 (15) Neither appropriate nor inappropriate: 19 (16) Appropriate: 20 (17) Strongly appropriate: 17 (15)

Qualitative Feedback from Professionals on Draft Good Practice Statements

Respondents were invited to provide qualitative comments on the Draft Good Practice Statements for chronic conditions, of which n=34 professionals offered qualitative comment. A summary of key points from the descriptive analysis is shown below. The dominant themed issues that were noted across feedback were 1. General appropriateness, 2. The importance of simplicity and accessibility, 3. The need to ‘start low’ and gradually increase, 4. Safety considerations, and 5. Need to address ‘fear’ of physical activity. Further description of this feedback is found in Table 7. The actionable findings from this element of the consultation were brought forward to the National Stakeholder Meeting to assist in informing refinement of the draft document at subsequent stages. Appendix 2 provides a link to the finalised Good Practice Statements that were used in the developed guidelines.

Table 7. Professional qualitative feedback on draft good practice statements

Theme issues	Description	Quote example
General appropriateness	Many respondents shared positive sentiment about the prospect of Guidelines accompanied by Good Practice Statements, and their broad need.	<i>“I feel these are appropriate in addition to the guidelines”.</i> <i>“I think these are very helpful and will allow patients to feel that they can achieve some physical activity goals.”</i>
The importance of simplicity and accessibility	Pertaining to language, respondents emphasised the importance of accessible language within Good Practice Statements. Respondents offered some alternative wording suggestions in areas.	

A need to 'start low' and gradually increase	Respondents highlighted the need to prioritise Statements that promoted 'low threshold' physical activity, noting that high volume guidelines may have deleterious impacts on activity.	<i>"I believe in starting off small and building on success, telling someone they should do more than they are able and this can cause disappointment and they may stop completely"</i> <i>"When it is difficult to achieve, it is often difficult to sustain. Leading to poor outcomes regarding consistency and motivation. This can also foster a negative association to exercise."</i>
Safety considerations	Two respondents highlighted the need for Advice on Warm-up/Cool-down. Many respondents sought more detail on Professional advice Statements.	<i>"To include advise on warm up & cool down".</i> <i>"More information needed on professional advice"</i>
Need to address 'fear' of physical activity	Respondents valued Good Practice Statements that addressed fear of physical activity, and recommended this as a good frame for Statements.	<i>"Similarly, statements 6 -10 address removing the 'fear' around exercises and the questions of 'can I/what if'. I like how these take a graded response and allow for more individuality and personalised approach"</i>

Professional Rating of Appropriateness of Population Specific Considerations

Professional stakeholder respondents were asked to indicate the level of appropriateness for Draft Specific Population Considerations which were developed to provide nuanced tailoring for issues that have specificity across particular chronic conditions. Consistent levels of appropriateness were found across all nine Draft Population Specific Considerations. One Draft Population Specific Consideration on Obesity yielded slightly less consistent scores, which were explored in subsequent stages. Table 8 below details a breakdown of responses across nine Draft Population Specific Considerations. The Draft Population Considerations that were used during this stage can be found in Appendix 1.

Table 8. Professional respondents rating of appropriateness of draft population specific consideration

Draft Population Specific Considerations	Appropriateness Rating N (%)
1 Cardiovascular disease Consideration 1	Strongly inappropriate: 1 Inappropriate: 7 (6) Neither appropriate nor inappropriate: 7 (6) Appropriate: 30 (26) Strongly appropriate: 19 (16)
2 Cardiovascular disease Consideration 2	Strongly inappropriate: 1 Inappropriate: 7 (6) Neither appropriate nor inappropriate: 7 (6) Appropriate: 30 (26) Strongly appropriate: 19 (16)

3 Respiratory condition Consideration 1	Strongly inappropriate: 1 Inappropriate: 0 Neither appropriate nor inappropriate: 3 (2) Appropriate: 29 (25) Strongly appropriate: 32 (27)
4 Diabetes Consideration 1	Strongly inappropriate: 1 Inappropriate: 2 Neither appropriate nor inappropriate: 5 (4) Appropriate: 25 (22) Strongly appropriate: 30 (26)
5 Obesity/Increase adiposity Consideration 1	Strongly inappropriate: 4 (3) Inappropriate: 7 (6) Neither appropriate nor inappropriate: 11 (9) Appropriate: 27 (23) Strongly appropriate: 19 (16)
6 Mental health Consideration 1	Strongly inappropriate: 0 Inappropriate: 2 Neither appropriate nor inappropriate: 2 Appropriate: 16 (14) Strongly appropriate: 45 (38)
7 Cancer Consideration 1	Strongly inappropriate: 1 Inappropriate: 3 (<3) Neither appropriate nor inappropriate: 1 Appropriate: 26 (22) Strongly appropriate: 26 (22)
8 Frailty Consideration 1	Strongly inappropriate: 1 Inappropriate: 3 (<3) Neither appropriate nor inappropriate: 3 (<3) Appropriate: 27 (23) Strongly appropriate: 39 (33)
9 Neurological condition Consideration 1	Strongly inappropriate: 1 Inappropriate: 2 Neither appropriate nor inappropriate: 2 Appropriate: 30 (26) Strongly appropriate: 28 (24)

Qualitative Feedback on Draft Population Specific Considerations from Professionals

A total of N=18 professional respondents provided qualitative feedback on the Draft Population Specific Considerations. Descriptive qualitative analysis indicated three overarching themes within the data. These themes were, 1. 'The importance of specific tailoring', 2. 'Clarification on health outcomes, and 3. A need for clarity regarding the target populations. A summary of these findings are below.

The importance of specific tailoring

The first theme centred on the importance of specific tailoring within the guidelines. Respondents emphasised the importance of condition-specific nuance within the guidelines.

“Difficult to generalise as exercise needs to be tailored to the individual – e.g., severity of neurological condition and other factors.”

Clarification of health outcomes

Acknowledging the draft nature of these Considerations, it is noteworthy that some comments challenged the clarity and accuracy of linking exercise solely with key outcomes like weight loss or improved cardiovascular function, as was perceived by the respondents. This highlighted a need for enhanced clarity, and consideration of respondent interpretation of Considerations put forward.

“I think the weight loss one is not clear. What is the intended message? That if someone is overweight, they will benefit from losing weight via exercise?”

“The message that physical activity alone will improve cardiovascular health in every case is too strong – many factors are involved.”

These responses point to the need for more nuanced interpretation of Considerations put forward.

A need for clarity regarding the target population

Again, acknowledging that respondents were feeding back on Draft Consideration, there were some professionals that highlighted a perception that many people with chronic conditions may require professional oversight when recommending physical activity to individuals with complex or serious health issues. This highlighted a need for enhanced clarity on future iterations to draw strong distinctions where professional oversight may be warranted, and to also clearly allay concerns that chronic conditions should not act as a barrier to initiating physical activity.

“Should these people be under specialist care where exercise can be part of a supervised treatment plan?”

“People with metastatic cancers should see a clinical specialist physiotherapist, bony metastases should be checked / patients advised accordingly”

A few participants expressed caution about the nature of wording within some of the Draft Considerations, pointing to a need for caution about overstating the benefits of exercise, especially in the context of severe or progressive conditions. Whilst the guidelines developed here are indeed

public health guidelines, the point is nonetheless important to consider with respect to how Considerations may be interpreted by professional stakeholders.

“Again if any of the above statements could be interpreted as suggesting exercise cures or significantly alters disease progression that could be misleading.”

Understandably, some participants desired a broadening of the scope of Considerations, some of which fell outside the remit of the project, but indicating the policy need for such guidelines.

“Need people with intellectual disabilities mentioned”

The final Population Specific Considerations that were adopted following refinement during subsequent stages are in Appendix 2.

Summary

In relation to the chronic conditions Guidelines, Good Practice Statements and Specific Population Considerations, most respondents from the professional cohort found the guidelines clear (77%) and appropriate (60%). Similar high levels of appropriateness were also reported for the Good Practice Statements and Specific Population Considerations/Recommendations. Qualitative feedback highlighted a desire for more specific guidance accounting for condition nuance, clearer more accessible and inclusive messaging, risk, and accessibility. Professionals commented on the value of tailored support, including considerations and collaboration with healthcare professionals among more severe conditions. The actionable findings from this element of the consultation were brought forward to the National Stakeholder Meeting to assist in informing refinement of the draft document on chronic conditions.

The Messages for Professionals

The last section of the stakeholder consultation for professionals was to invite them to rate the messages for health and social care and sport and physical activity professionals working with people with chronic conditions. Respondents were invited to rate the messages based on relevance, feasibility, support in delivering information, overall helpfulness and likelihood of use in practice.

As can be seen in Table 9 below, the majority of professionals found the Draft Messages relevant and reported that they were likely to use them in practice, whilst acknowledging survey drop-out (likely due to questionnaire burden). While the messages were seen as helpful overall, a considerable portion of respondents were neutral about the ability of Messages to support professionals in delivering information.

Table 9. Overview of rating of draft messages for professionals

Criteria	Strongly disagree N(%)	Somewhat disagree N(%)	Neither agree nor disagree N(%)	Somewhat agree N(%)	Strongly agree N(%)
Relevance to Role	0	0	1 (<1)	16 (14)	58 (50)
Realistic and Feasible to Apply	0	1 (<1)	7 (6)	31 (27)	35 (30)
Support to Deliver Information	3 (2)	6 (5)	28 (24)	18 (15)	16 (14)
Overall Helpfulness	0	1 (<1)	3 (2)	30 (26)	41 (35)
Likelihood of Use in Practice	0	0	1 (<1)	30 (26)	44 (38)

Qualitative Feedback on Draft Messages for Professionals

Professional respondents were also offered an opportunity to give qualitative feedback, which were analysed with descriptive thematic analysis. A total of N=19 respondents provided qualitative comment on the Draft Messages for professionals. The comments reflect both commendation and constructive critique, highlighting areas for improvement in clarity, safety, and inclusivity that were carried forward into subsequent stages of the development. There were four overarching themes identified within the qualitative data here.

Positive feedback on messages purpose

Some feedback praised the inclusive and supportive tone of the messaging, particularly in acknowledging barriers that people with chronic conditions face, particularly at the point of activity commencement.

“I really like all of the above – it highlights that doing some activity is better than none and that benefits can be gained regardless of weight loss.”

A need to enhance practical advice within messages

A number of respondents expressed the need for clearer, more actionable guidance.

“More concrete examples of what counts as moderate or vigorous activity would help.”

“Could include examples of home-based activities or chair exercises.”

“There should be more of an emphasis on weight training and its importance for people with chronic disease”

Some of the sentiment in this regard pertained to desire for more safety information to be provided to professionals within the messages.

“Include advice around warm up and cool down for cardiac patients and people with long-term conditions.”

Language inclusivity and precision

Whilst acknowledging the draft nature of the Messages provided to respondents in the survey, some respondents commented on the clarity and specificity of language used, especially with terms that they interpreted as being potentially misunderstood.

“‘Should attain moderate intensity physical activity’ – what does this mean in this context?”

“Sedentary needs to be explained. The message could be misinterpreted as ‘you must move every 30 mins’, which may not be achievable.”

“The content of all these points is accurate but there is a risk that professionals would inconsistently or poorly adapt it into plain English, if they do not have examples of appropriate language.”

These observations call for careful consideration of language particularly with respect to clinical or technical terms to mitigate any confusion. These points were taken forward into subsequent stages of the process.

Balance of realism and motivation

There was a strong call for messaging that strikes a balance between aspirational goals and realistic expectations, especially for people with chronic conditions or disabilities.

“We need to be careful not to shame people who are not able to meet the guidelines.”

“Emphasise that small amounts of movement still have value – this is very encouraging for people who struggle with motivation or energy.”

The finalised messages that were adopted following all stages of refinement are found in Appendix 2.

Summary

In summary, the Draft Messages for professionals were overall well received by the professional cohort that responded, with a high likelihood of their use in practice reported among the majority. A number of respondents indicated a level of neutrality in terms of their ability to support professionals to deliver information, thus indicating a point for further refinement in subsequent stages. Qualitative feedback highlighted positive sentiment on the inclusive tone of the proposed messages, particularly the emphasis that ‘any movement is beneficial’. However, they stressed the need for greater clarity in language, with terms like “sedentary”, seen as potentially confusing without further explanation. Some comments warned against a prescriptive tone, noting a risk of alienating individuals with complex limitations. There was a clear call to ensure messages are supportive, rather than stigmatising, and to reflect the realities of those living with chronic conditions. Practical, relatable examples were suggested. Overall, messages should strike a balance between motivation and realism, empowering the support of people at all levels and abilities. The findings from the online professional consultation were utilised in the National Stakeholder Meeting (Stage 4) to refine the draft guidelines for people with chronic conditions.

Stage 4: National Stakeholder Meeting

The draft Guidelines developed in Stage 1 and the stakeholder feedback gathered in Stage 2 and 3 were combined to form the basis of a National Stakeholder Meeting. The meeting took place in-person in Dublin, and brought together stakeholders from across multiple relevant sectors. Invitations were extended to a confined number of representatives from different stakeholder categories and to additional interested and relevant parties. Stakeholder mapping was performed with the HSE to identify the key bodies, organisations and professions to be represented. Stakeholders (n=32) representing the health sector, advocacy groups, academics and physical activity specialist and providers attended. Following an opening address from the National Lead for Healthy Eating Active Living (HSE), there was a presentation from the project team which provided context on the development of the Guidelines in terms of their purpose, structure and context to focus discussions on refinement of the Guidelines as opposed to broader discussions in the context of physical activity for people with chronic conditions. While valid points were raised during stakeholder consultation in relation to accessibility and availability of exercise professionals and physiotherapy, this was not within the scope of the guidelines to address, but was acknowledged as a broader recommendation. It was also clearly specified that the guidelines have a public health focus and would be constrained to broader recommendations as opposed to a detailed guide on clinical exercise prescription, which is challenging in the context of health conditions as it was acknowledged. It was highlighted that the guidelines would also maintain alignment with the National Physical Activity and Sedentary Behaviour Guidelines, 'Every Move Counts' and should maintain alignment with the guidelines for pregnancy and postpartum where relevant.

Following the noted background information, stakeholders were presented with the process on the development of draft physical activity and sedentary behaviour guidelines for chronic conditions, as per aforementioned steps within this report (Evidence review, Drafting and project team review, Stakeholder consultations). Stakeholders were then presented with a summary of the results from the online stakeholder consultation surveys outlined in Stage 3 of this report.

Informed by the development process up to this point, a series of round table discussion session with stakeholders (attending the National Stakeholder Meeting) facilitated by the project team then took place as follows: 'Discussion round 1' was about the Draft Guidelines and Good Practice Statements, with a particular focus on Appropriateness, Safety, Comprehensiveness/missing information, and Usefulness to support activity in people with chronic conditions; 'Discussion round 2' was about the Draft Specific Population Considerations, with a particular focus on, Appropriateness, Safety, Comprehensiveness/missing information, Usefulness and Challenges (which included managing 'tone'

on certain conditions, where prior feedback indicated a need for greater clarity); ‘Discussion round 3’ was about Draft Messages for professionals and addressed, Usefulness, Supportive Guidance, and Comprehensiveness/missing information, ‘Discussion round 4’ was about Draft Messages for the end user with chronic conditions and addressed, Inclusivity, Clarity, Supportive Guidance, and Comprehensiveness/missing information.

Following on from this, a summary of ‘Issues raised’ and further discussion points were collated. These were fed back to the stakeholder groups. Where possible issues raised that required clarity were addressed at the meeting by members of the project team and recommendations were taken back to the working group for further refinement of the guidelines. Table 10 outlines a summary of the outcomes from this stage.

Table 10. Summary of national stakeholder meeting discussion and ‘issues raised’

Discussion Round 1: Draft Guidelines and Good Practice Statements	
‘Issues raised’	Outcome
Use simpler, consistent language; clarify terms (e.g. “talk test”, “exercise professionals”, “more advanced”); provide definitions and worked examples.	All language were reviewed by the project team, and contextualized with international examples. Appendices and graphics were also developed to support scientific comprehension. Signposting and clarification added to the document to support comprehension around vague terms like “advanced”.
Offer practical advice within guidelines.	Greater clarity were added to ‘How to get active’ section of Good Practice Statements, with particular emphasis on physical activity commencement.
Emphasise benefits for all, including ‘late starters’. For instance, avoid language like “at least” and replace with “up to” to reduce pressure; highlight enjoyment and real-life relevance; acknowledge effort in starting small.	Post review of guidelines supported this. Language recommendations to be more supportive of people with low levels of activity, recognising ability variation were integrated. Good Practice Statement order were amended to emphasize commencement at low levels of activity.
Make Good Practice Statements shorter and punchier; Consider order of Statements for logical flow.	All language were reviewed by the project team with a view to maximizing conciseness. Ordering were reviewed by project team. Statements were further categorized into “How to

	get active” and “Risk reduction” sub domains to support logical comprehension.
Revise Good Practice Statement 11 which contained recommendations for offsetting deleterious health impacts of sedentary behaviour.	This Good Practice Statement were amended to focus on supporting habitual physical activity over time.
Remove reference to medication interactions.	Added clarity in Risk Reduction – Good Practice Statements on contraindications and warning signs.

Discussion Round 2: Draft Specific Population Considerations

“Obesity” terminology adoption, rather than prior “adiposity” were recommended. Recent national guidance on obesity 2022 were suggested as a referent point (73).	Terminology and additional evidence source were reviewed and amended accordingly.
There is a need to frame Obesity Consideration about the benefits of physical activity as separate from weight reduction.	The wording of Obesity Considerations were reviewed, and emphasis put to fitness and health benefit. It is noted that Messages further implicate a need to divert focus from weight loss.
Suggestion to acknowledge Cancer related fatigue.	Cancer related fatigue were specifically addressed within refinement of Specific Population Consideration for living with and beyond cancer.
Suggestion to amend wording of Draft Cancer Consideration to be in the positive (promote movement), rather than the negative (avoid sedentary behaviour).	Positive framing adopted within refinement of Consideration for living with and beyond cancer.

Discussion Round 3: Draft Messages for Professionals

Some stakeholders acknowledged the range and diversity of knowledge among HCPs and that there is a need for training to better support HCPs to promote PA.	Whilst outside of the direct scope of the current guidelines, this feedback were relevant to messages developed for policy makers.
Consider Appendix for more detailed explanations.	Suggestion adopted in completed Guidelines.
Suggestion to ‘de –medicalise’ Messages, and negate fear. Instead of saying “There is evidence”, say “PA can”...	Messages were reviewed by the project team and language refinement were carried reflecting suggestion.
Provide practical information when referring to technical terms, e.g. vigorous, what is it?	Appendix added to clarify complex terminology that were maintained for Guideline fidelity.
Refine language to support professionals to address fear of PA among people with chronic conditions.	Messages to the professionals were reviewed by the project team and refined in the context of a ‘support role’.

Consider incorporation of a Message that reflects sentiment 'significant benefits can be accrued among the most inactive persons'.	Recommendation considered in the context of international evidence. Message 3 for professionals within the finalised Guidelines reflects recommendation.
Align phrasing of Messages for each professional group, creating new Messages where there is divergence in the recommendations.	Guidelines have been refined aligning Messages.
There is a need for Messages to empower professionals that PA is a safe and well evidenced management tool.	Empowerment Messages that address align with this suggestion have been prioritised within the Messages. Phraseology has been reviewed by the project team in context of emphasising the recommendation.
Discussion Round 4: Draft Messages for End-user with chronic conditions	
An important first message for the population should be that 'any physical activity, is better than none'.	The Messages for end-users were reviewed in context. Every Move Counts were prioritised as the first message (detailed in subsequent Stage).
A suggestion to have the same messaging for end users and professionals was made.	Alignment in messaging was undertaken where possible, acknowledging that the aim of each were different. Ordering was also subject to subsequent prioritization work.
Suggestion to use simpler, consistent language.	All language were reviewed by the project team with a view to plain language where possible, these were contextualized with international examples. Reference to 'sedentary behaviour' were changed in user Messages to 'sitting time'.
Suggestion to 'theme' Messages to make them more consumable.	Messages were divided into themes of 'Perception and Motivation' and 'Knowledge' in line with National Physical activity Guidelines prior to finalisation.
Suggestion to integrate more 'positive framing' of Messages.	The project team made efforts to increase 'positive framing' in Messages, and in-turn reduce 'negative framing' Messaging.
Infographic or cartoon style images were suggested for the end user Messages.	Broader infographic and visual messaging is being undertaken by the Health Eating Active Living (HSE) team.
Consider the limited impact of a large number of Messages.	The project team carefully considered the volume of Messages. The largest number of Messages are in

	relation to knowledge, and it should be considered that many are considered necessary for safety reasons.
The Messages should avoid, where possible being prescriptive in their framing (e.g. people with chronic conditions <i>should do...</i> ”).	Draft Message 10 and 12 (‘Speak with HCP if unexpected symptoms’; ‘Avoidance of prolonged sedentariness’) were subject to review and revision.
Consistency of language across the document required.	Careful consideration of consistent and accessible language were considered this in the document finalisation.
<i>HCP = Healthcare professional; PA = physical activity.</i>	

Stage 5 Consolidation and Refinement

The project team considered findings from the National Stakeholder Meeting and subsequent feedback from the HSE Healthy Eating Active Living Programme team and the team from the Integrated Care Programme for Prevention and Management of Chronic Disease, HSE, before agreeing the final Guidelines and Messages drafting. Table 10 above outlines the rationale for some key amendments. The project team also undertook a final review of message and statement order within sections. A notable addition to the guidelines were messages for policy and decision makers included to reflect broader level recommendations from stakeholders to support the implementation of the Guidelines. These can be found as part of the finalised document in Appendix 2.

At final draft stage, the project team were tasked with identifying the messages recommended for prioritisation from the full set of messages published in Appendix 2. In summary, the most useful messages within the Messages for people with chronic conditions were related to broad universal benefit of physical activity across conditions and for sitting to be replaced with any movement, where possible.

The most useful Messages within the Messages for health and social-care professionals were related to benefits of activity outweighing the risks of inactivity, and the most impactful benefits being accrued for inactive persons becoming somewhat active.

Among Messages for sport and physical activity/exercise professionals, equally prioritised Messages were related to broad universal benefit of physical activity across conditions, and the benefits of activity outweighing the risks of inactivity. This process allowed for order finalisation of Messages within Guidelines (see Table 11). This process were followed by further Guideline refinement, where the subsequent Guideline iteration were then sent forward to the HSE Healthy Eating Active Living team, in addition to national clinical leads and members of the Integrated Care Programme for the Prevention and Management of Chronic Disease for final review ahead of final agreement on the developed Guidelines and Messages. Following this, the finalised guideline documents were submitted to the HSE for design. These finalised National Physical Activity and Sedentary Behaviour Guidelines for Ireland for living with chronic conditions are available via the link in Appendix 2.

Table 11. Ranking of messages by project team

Message type	Top 3 Messages (Ranked by usefulness)
<p>Messages for Chronic conditions (end user)</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Physical activity is very beneficial for a range of chronic conditions, reducing the progression of many conditions, improving fitness, mental health and quality of life. (AND) Try to limit the amount of time you spend inactive, such as sitting still. Replacing sitting time with any movement is beneficial 3. Engage in both muscle strengthening activity and aerobic physical activity for substantial health benefit. (AND) For most, it is not necessary to obtain medical clearance prior to beginning light or moderate-intensity physical activity not exceeding the demands of brisk walking or everyday living. You can then progress this over time.
<p>Messages for Health and Social Care Professionals</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The benefits of being active for individuals with chronic conditions far outweigh the risks. 2. The greatest benefits occur when totally inactive individuals become somewhat active, with further benefits gained through further increases in physical activity. Every Move Counts. 3. Leverage opportunities to ‘make every contact count’. People are more likely to engage in physical activity if their healthcare professional recommends it.
<p>Messages for Sport and Physical Activity Professionals</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. There is strong scientific evidence supporting the importance of physical activity for people with chronic conditions. There is evidence that physical activity can reduce mortality, slow the progression of certain conditions, prevent further complications and the development of comorbidities, relieve symptoms, support self-management, enhance functional capacity, improve key mental health outcomes and improve quality of life. (AND) The benefits of being active for individuals with chronic conditions far outweigh the risks. 3. Those who cannot meet the guidelines should begin physical activity with small durations of moderate intensity activity and build the duration gradually over time. They can accumulate physical activity over the day.

(AND)

There is a need for equal emphasis between muscle strengthening activities and aerobic physical activity.

AND = Equal scoring

Conclusion

This report outlines the process of developing National Physical Activity and Sedentary Behaviour Guidelines for people living well with chronic conditions, to accompany the National Physical Activity and Sedentary Behaviour Guidelines for Ireland, 'Every Move Counts'. The development of these Guidelines represents a significant advance in inclusive public health policy. Through a rigorous process of comprehensive evidence review, project team refinement and drafting, wide-ranging stakeholder consultation, national stakeholder meeting and iterative refinement, these guidelines have been shaped by high quality evidence and the input of a large number of key stakeholders reflecting the community of people living with chronic conditions in Ireland and relevant professionals working in practice and policy.

The key strengths of these guidelines lie in their clear and actionable recommendations that take account of the diverse heterogeneity of individuals living with chronic conditions. They acknowledge, as best as is possible, variations in health status, physical capacity, and personal context, offering a mechanism that supports individuals living with chronic conditions, and professionals in their work to promote physical activity. The messaging encourages physical activity as a tool for health management, dispelling risk perceptions and recognises the importance of monitoring, and individualised care.

While the guidelines maintain a broad public health perspective, they strive to provide enough specificity to be useful across a range of prominent chronic conditions that have previously served as a barrier to physical activity. Importantly, these guidelines attempt to recognise between stages of condition progression, recovery and shifting ability therein.

Separate messaging has been developed for individuals with chronic conditions, health and social care professionals and sport exercise/physical activity professionals, reflecting the different roles each plays in supporting safe and sustainable physical activity. The inclusion of policy level recommendations is a deliberate move to advocate for systemic change, calling for investment in infrastructure, training, and community-based programs that make physical activity accessible and inclusive for all.

Looking ahead, the success of these guidelines will depend on dissemination efforts, continuous evaluation, and the co-creation of supportive tools and resources. Embedding these guidelines into clinical practice and national health promotion strategies will empower individuals with chronic conditions to engage in physical activity safely, effectively, and equitably.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: Draft Physical Activity and Sedentary Behaviour Guidelines for Ireland for People Living with Chronic Conditions Circulated for Stakeholder Consultation

Draft Physical Activity and Sedentary Behaviour Guidelines for People Living with Chronic Conditions

All adults living with a chronic condition, or multiple chronic conditions should be physically active. By engaging in regular physical activity, people living with chronic conditions can slow disease progression, prevent further complications and the development of comorbidities, relieve symptoms, support disease management, enhance functional capacity and improve quality of life.

Below indicated are national public health level guidelines intended for people in Ireland of varying abilities living with well managed chronic conditions. People undergoing acute treatment phases of their condition, those not yet maintained on medication or those with medical contraindications to do physical activity should seek further advice from a health care practitioner prior to commencing physical activity.

Guidelines:

It is recommended that

- All adults including older adults with chronic conditions should undertake regular muscle strengthening activities and aerobic physical activity.
- Adults living with a chronic condition should, throughout the week, undertake at least 2 hours and 30 mins to 5 hours of moderate intensity aerobic physical activity; or at least 1 hour and 15 minutes to 2 hours and 30 mins of vigorous-intensity aerobic physical activity; or a combination of both, for substantial health benefits.
- Adults living with a chronic condition should undertake muscle strengthening activities at moderate or greater intensity that involve all major muscle groups on 2 or more days per week
- Older adults living with a chronic condition should also undertake multicomponent balance and strength activities on 3 or more days of the week to enhance functional capacity and prevent falls

- Adults living with a chronic condition should limit the amount of time spent being sedentary. Replacing sedentary time with physical activity of any intensity (including light intensity) provides health benefits

Good Practice Statements

1. When not able to meet the above recommendations, adults with chronic conditions should aim to engage in physical activity according to their abilities.
2. Inactive adults with chronic conditions should start by doing small amounts of physical activity and gradually increase the frequency, duration and eventually the intensity over time.
3. Adherence to long-term physical activity is essential for health gain so the mode of physical activity should be one that is enjoyed.
4. The 'talk test' is a simple and effective method to gauge moderate intensity physical activity if trying to remain in the moderate zone. During moderate-intensity exercise, it should be possible to carry on a conversation with a little difficulty but not sing.
5. A physical activity specialist or exercise professional may be of value in assisting with the types and amounts of activity appropriate for individual needs, abilities, functional limitations/ complications, medications, and overall treatment plan.
6. Pre-exercise medical clearance is generally unnecessary for most individuals prior to beginning light or moderate-intensity physical activity not exceeding the demands of brisk walking or everyday living.
7. Individuals with signs and symptoms of cardiovascular, diabetes or kidney disease (e.g. chest pain, unusual shortness of breath, loss of consciousness, unusual fatigue) should seek medical advice before commencing a physical activity programme
8. Adults who have more advanced chronic conditions, who require frequent visits for medical management and who are not stable on medications should seek medical advice before commencing a physical activity programme.
9. Consultation with an appropriate health care professional should happen if unexpected changes or worsening symptoms occur with physical activity.
10. Adults with chronic conditions may need to consider appropriate environmental conditions and clothing and footwear for physical activity to accommodate treatment and condition related symptoms and experiences.
11. Adults with chronic conditions who spend prolonged periods in sedentary behaviour should strive to do more than the recommended guidelines of moderate to vigorous physical activity to reduce negative health impacts.

Specific Population Considerations

Cardiovascular disease

Physical activity on most days of the week is preferable for individuals with hypertension as some of the benefits from each activity bout are short lived.

Intermittent physical activity, i.e. short physical activity bouts with rest periods, may be more tolerable for some individuals, including those with peripheral arterial disease.

Respiratory Conditions

Intermittent physical activity, i.e. short physical activity bouts with rest periods, may be more tolerable for some individuals with respiratory conditions. Breathlessness, related to exertion, should not necessarily be feared or avoided.

Diabetes

Physical activity on most days of the week is preferable for individuals with diabetes as some of the benefits from each activity bout in terms of glucose control and insulin action are short lived.

Increased adiposity or at risk

Greater volumes of physical activity, at or beyond the upper end of the physical activity guidelines, may be needed to prevent weight gain and for substantial weight loss in the absence of other interventions.

Mental Health Conditions

Physical activity that is autonomously motivated and that creates opportunities for social interaction will optimise the mental health benefits. Prolonged sedentary time should be avoided.

Living with and beyond cancer: When cancer-related fatigue and other treatment side are present and physical function is low, improvements can be achieved with lower levels of activity than the recommended physical activity guidelines, increasing slowly over time. Prolonged sedentary time should be avoided.

Risk of frailty: Muscle strengthening physical activity should be prioritised over aerobic physical activity where a person is at risk of frailty or has reduced muscle mass and is not able to meet the recommended physical activity guidelines.

Neurological Conditions: Multi-component physical activity on 3 or more days per week that focuses on flexibility, balance and functional movement activity at a moderate intensity or greater should be prioritised for individuals with neurological conditions such as Multiple Sclerosis or Parkinson's Disease. Prolonged sedentary time should be avoided.

Messages for Users

1. Physical activity is very beneficial for a range of chronic conditions, reducing the progression of that condition, improving fitness, quality of life, mental health and wellbeing.
2. If living with a chronic condition, you should engage in both muscle strengthening activity and aerobic physical activity for substantial health benefit
3. You can meet the aerobic physical activity recommendations by undertaking 2 hours and 30 minutes – 5 hours of moderate intensity physical activity (e.g. walking, running, swimming, cycling or hand cycling) per week or 1 hour 15 minutes to 2 hours and 30 minutes of vigorous intensity physical activity per week, or a combination of both
4. You can meet the muscle strengthening recommendations by undertaking activities involving resistance equipment, resistance bands or body weight exercises that target the major muscle groups on two or more days per week.
5. Even small amounts of physical activity are better for your health and mental health than not doing any physical activity. If you cannot meet the physical activity guidelines straight away, you should start with the maximum amount of activity that is tolerable for you.
6. The 'talk test' is a simple and effective method of trying to ensure that physical activity remains at moderate intensity. During moderate-intensity activity, you should be able to carry on a conversation but not sing. If you find it difficult to hold a conversation, you may be exercising at a vigorous intensity. Vigorous intensity physical activity will leave you more breathless but is not harmful. You can progress to this over time.
7. For most, it is not necessary to obtain medical clearance prior to beginning light or moderate-intensity physical activity not exceeding the demands of brisk walking or everyday living.
8. You can gradually increase the duration and frequency of physical activity over time before eventually increasing the intensity.
9. If you think you have an advanced form of a chronic condition or have warning signs of cardiovascular disease complications (e.g. chest pain, unusual shortness of breath, loss of consciousness, unusual fatigue), you must seek medical advice prior to commencing physical activity.
10. You should speak with a healthcare professional if unexpected changes occur or symptoms relevant to your condition worsen from physical activity
11. Do physical activity that you enjoy for long-term adherence – all physical activity is beneficial for your health and wellbeing.
12. You should avoid prolonged periods of sitting and lounging flat, you should break up sedentary time with activity of any type, by standing up and moving around.

Messages for Health and Social Care Professionals and Practitioners

1. There is strong scientific evidence supporting the importance of physical activity for people with chronic conditions. There is evidence that physical activity can reduce mortality, slow certain disease progression, prevent further complications and the development of comorbidities, relieve symptoms, support disease management, enhance functional capacity, improve key mental health outcomes and improve quality of life.
2. The guidelines recommend muscle strengthening and aerobic activities for individuals with chronic conditions. The guidelines for aerobic activity can be achieved by a combination of moderate and vigorous intensity aerobic physical activity. The guidelines give equal emphasis to the need for muscle strengthening activities on two days of the week.
3. The guidelines support the concept that every move counts and that those who cannot attain the guidelines should undertake moderate intensity physical activity to the maximum possible amount.
4. Separate to physical activity, the guidelines emphasise that prolonged sedentary behaviour is also harmful to health for people with chronic conditions. The guidelines recommend breaking up sedentary behaviour and replacing with any physical activity including light intensity physical activity.
5. People with chronic conditions are ideally placed for behaviour change around physical activity and often desire direction to improve health status. They are more likely to engage in physical activity if their healthcare provider recommends it. Leverage these opportunities to make every contact count.
6. People with chronic conditions often experience complex barriers to physical activity, including low physical activity self-efficacy and fear of injury, which should be acknowledged when promoting physical activity.
7. The benefits of being active for individuals with chronic conditions far outweigh the risks, however there is a need to identify the individual starting point and to build up gradually.
8. The greatest risk of heart attack from physical activity occurs in habitually inactive individuals who suddenly undertake strenuous physical activity. It is therefore important to start off slowly and become habitually active over a period of months with gradual increases in duration and then intensity.
9. Weight loss alone is not a good rationale for promoting physical activity as weight loss from physical activity alone is small. Broader mental health, physical health and functional outcomes should be implicated in promoting physical activity.

Messages for Physical Activity/Sport Professionals and Practitioners

1. There is strong scientific evidence supporting the importance of physical activity for people with chronic conditions. There is evidence that physical activity can reduce mortality, slow certain disease progression, prevent further complications and the development of comorbidities, relieve symptoms, support disease management, enhance functional capacity, improve key mental health outcomes and improve quality of life.
2. The guidelines recommend muscle strengthening and aerobic activities for individuals with chronic conditions. The guidelines for aerobic activity can be achieved by a combination of moderate and vigorous intensity aerobic physical activity. The guidelines give equal emphasis for the need to do muscle strengthening activities on two days of the week.
3. The guidelines support the concept that every move counts and that those who cannot attain the guidelines should undertake moderate intensity physical activity to the maximum possible amount.
4. Separate to physical activity, the guidelines emphasise that prolonged sedentary behaviour is also harmful to health for people with chronic conditions. The guidelines recommend breaking up sedentary behaviour and replacing with any physical activity including light intensity physical activity.
5. The benefits of being active for individuals with chronic conditions far outweigh the risks, however there is a need to identify the individual starting point and to build up gradually.
6. The greatest risk of heart attack from physical activity occurs in habitually inactive individuals who suddenly undertake strenuous physical activity. It is therefore important to start off slowly and become habitually active over a period of months with gradual increases in the volume of physical activity (e.g. duration), and then intensity.
7. Weight loss alone is not a good rationale for promoting physical activity, as weight loss from physical activity alone is small. Broader mental health, physical health and functional outcomes should be emphasised in promoting physical activity.
8. It is not necessary to send most individuals with chronic conditions for pre-exercise medical clearance, particularly when commencing light or moderate-intensity physical activity not exceeding the demands of brisk walking or everyday living. Pre-exercise clearance can act as a barrier to commencing physical activity.
9. It is important to seek clearance and/or medical advice if participants have signs and symptoms of cardiovascular, diabetes or kidney problems (e.g. chest pain, unusual shortness of breath, loss of consciousness, unusual fatigue), require frequent visits for medical management or are not stable on medications.
10. It is important to consult with an appropriate health care professional if unexpected changes occur or symptoms get worse from doing physical activity.
11. You should assist participants in understanding differences between moderate and vigorous intensity aerobic physical activity using approaches such as the “talk test” or

“rate of perceived exertion scale” or “dyspnea rating scale”. This should be done without presenting vigorous physical activity as harmful.

12. To increase physical activity in people with chronic conditions, incremental increases in frequency and duration should be prioritised ahead of incremental increases in intensity.
13. People with chronic conditions often experience complex barriers to physical activity, including low physical activity self-efficacy and fear of injury, which should be acknowledged when promoting physical activity to these people.
14. Physical activity movements may need to be adapted for many individuals with chronic conditions due to movement restrictions, joint degeneration, pain, motor control and surgeries. It is important to be sensitive to these movement considerations and be capable of adapting physical activity when necessary.

Appendix 2: Link to Published National Physical Activity and Sedentary Behaviour Guidelines for Ireland for People Living with Chronic Conditions with the Final Guidelines and Messages

<https://www.hse.ie/eng/about/who/healthwellbeing/our-priority-programmes/health/every-move-counts/hse-physical-activity-guidelines-for-chronic-conditions.pdf>

Appendix 3: Agenda for National Stakeholder Consultation Meeting

12.30 – 1.30	Registration and Lunch
1.30 – 1.40	Opening of the Chronic Disease Session <i>Dr. Sarah M. O'Brien, HSE</i>
1.40 – 1.55	Purpose, Structure and Content of the Guidelines <i>Prof. Michael Harrison, SETU</i>
1.55 – 2.15	Development of the Draft Guidelines and Messages <i>Dr. Evan Matthews, SETU</i>
2.15 – 2.50	Discussion 1: The guidelines; Good practices statements; Specific population considerations <i>Stakeholders</i>
2.50 – 3.15	Discussion 2: Messages for health & social care professionals <i>and</i> exercise professionals <i>Stakeholders</i>
3.15 – 3.35	Refreshments
3.35 – 4.05	Discussion 3: Messages for people living with chronic conditions <i>Stakeholders</i>
4.05 – 4.15	Close <i>Dr. Bláthín Casey, HSE</i>

Discussion 1/Session 1. The Guidelines; Good practices statements; Specific Population Considerations (14.15 – 14.50)

Intro points: We have structured sessions below broadly on issues that arose through survey respondents data (quantitative and qualitative). While there was broadly good agreement on the clarity and appropriateness of the Draft Guidelines, it is important to acknowledge that respondents would not have full context of the document when completing this survey.

The First Session is divided into two parts (Part 1 will take 20 minutes; Part 2 will take 10 minutes). Part 1 deals mainly with **The Guidelines** and **Good Practice Statements**. Part 2 deals with the **Specific Population Considerations**. Due to the volume of issues to be discussed in Session 1 Part 1, each Table will be given **2** unique Discussion points with questions, based on an issue that arose from our research. Part 1 will finish with all tables then dealing with Discussion point 5. Further guidance on the distribution of Discussion topics appears within relevant sections below.

Part 1: The Guidelines & Good Practice Statement: (15 Minutes – 7 min per Discussion point)

Here we want to focus on The Guidelines and on Good Practice Statements. The discussions here are drawn mainly on The Guidelines and Good Practice Statements that received lower agreement/consensus in the survey relative to others, or where qualitative data points to key issues of importance. In each of these, below, the Table host will take 1-2 minutes to outline the question and topic, drawing attention to the relevant section of the Draft Guidelines and Good Practice Statements.

Discussion Point 1 / Table 1, Table 2 and Table 3. *The appropriateness of the Guidelines and Good Practice Statement*

Question: Are the Draft Guidelines and Good Practice Statements appropriate? Do they pose a threat to the Motivation for inactive people with CC?

<i>Prompt for Table Host</i>	<i>Respondents qualitatively highlighted that the guidelines, as they currently appear, are ambitious for most people with chronic conditions, who tend to be more inactive.</i>
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Discussion Point 2 / Table 1, Table 2 and Table 3. *Addressing Sedentary Behaviour within the Guidelines and Good Practice Statements.*

Question: Do we satisfactorily address sedentary behaviour in both the Guidelines and Good Practice Statements?

<i>Prompt for Table Host</i>	<p>Qualitative points were raised and a ‘relatively’ lower consensus/agreement were reached on the Good Practice Statement about ‘<i>Doing MVPA to reduce risk from prolonged sedentary behaviour</i>’.</p> <p>What are the challenges presented with this statement? How can Good Practice Statement be enhanced if enhanced is required?</p>
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Discussion Point 3 / Table 4, Table 5 and Table 6. *The need for safe Guidelines and Good Practice Statements*

Question: Do the Draft Guidelines offer sufficient safety in recommending PA and reducing SB?

<i>Prompt for Table Host</i>	<p>Respondents highlighted the need for guidelines to ensure safe exercise practices for individuals with chronic conditions, the need to acknowledge flux states of wellness in CCs.</p> <p>A ‘relatively’ lower consensus/agreement were also reached on the Good Practice Statement about ‘<i>Pre-exercise medical clearance</i>’.</p> <p>How could Good Practice Statements be enhanced if enhancement is required?</p>
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Discussion Point 4/ Table 4, Table 5 and Table 6. *Signposting to professionals within the Guidelines and Good Practice Statements*

Question: How should these Guidelines (and Good Practice Statements) address signposting to relevant professionals?

<i>Prompt for Table Host</i>	<p>Qualitative data raised issues about Good Practice Statements, about ‘<i>Professional support</i>’.</p>
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ALL TABLES Discussion (5 Minutes)

Discussion Point 5 (all Tables). *Comprehensive Guidelines and Good Practice Statements*

Question: Are we missing anything from the Guidelines and Good Practices statements?

Part 2: Specific Population Considerations (10 minutes)

Here we want to focus on the **Considerations for Specific Population** groups proposed. In line with our brief, these need to be considered under the guise of Public/population Health Guidelines, rather than clinical guidelines. Here Tables are assigned **2** Discussion points again. Therefore, you should allocate five minutes to each.

Discussion Point 6 (Table 1, 2 3). *The challenge of delivering Considerations for Specific Populations within Public Health Guidance.*

5 Minutes

Question: Are these Considerations for Specific Populations appropriate in population level guideline?

<i>Prompt for Table Host</i>	<p>Many qualitative comments sought for these draft Considerations to go further, e.g. advocate for need for warm-up and cool down, need for additional information on strength training for people with neurological conditions, and the need for input of specialists</p> <p>How can we enhance these Considerations for Specific Population and also balance public health focus of guidelines for people living well with CCs?</p>
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Discussion Point 7 (Table 4, 5 6). The challenge of consideration for people with increased weight and adiposity

5 Minutes

Question: Do we appropriately address physical activity for people with increased weight and adiposity?

<i>Prompt for Table Host</i>	Qualitative comments suggest that this draft Consideration may be ambiguous about the role of PA in weight reduction. How may we improve this consideration to align with the wider Guidelines and Good Practice statements, and within the current evidence context?
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Discussion Point 8 (All Tables). Comprehensiveness of Specific Population Considerations

5 Minutes

Question: Are we missing anything from the Specific Population Considerations?

Session 1 Ends

Discussion 2/ Session 2. Messages for health & social care professionals and exercise professionals (14.50 – 15.15)

Intro points:

This is a shorter session than the previous. It seeks to look at key issues that arose in the Draft Messages for Health and Social Care Professionals and Draft Messages for Physical activity/Sport and Exercise Professionals. All tables will discuss all points in this Session.

Discussion Point 1: The usefulness of Guidelines and Messages to Support Practitioners/Professionals to deliver information about physical activity and sedentary behaviour.

Question: What do Messages that support practitioners and professionals look like?

8 Minutes

<i>Prompt for Table Host</i>	Looking at the Guidelines and Messages overall, participants had good agreement with respect to the 'Relevance', 'Feasibility', 'Helpfulness' and 'Likeliness to use them'. However when asked if the messages would support Practitioners to deliver Information about Physical activity, agreement was not as clear. Considering the Guidelines and Messages overall, how can we improve the Guidelines and Messages with respect to supporting Practitioners to deliver information about Physical activity? If at all.
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Discussion Point 2: Comprehensive Messages for Practitioners and Professionals.

8 Minutes

Question: Are we missing any other key Message relevant for Professionals and Practitioners (Health and Social Care and Physical activity/Sport)?

<i>Prompt for Table Host</i>	Looking at the Guidelines and Messages overall, is there any other significant issue relating to Risk and Safety that we have not adequately considered, that should be addressed following this meeting?
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Session 2 Ends

Discussion 3/Session 3. Messages for people living with chronic conditions (15.35 – 16.05)

The Messages for ‘Users’ are the aspect of the guidelines that are most likely to be consumed by people living well in communities with CC. Our qualitative work shows that these people are concerned about Clarity, Simplicity and therefore Inclusivity of the messages. All tables should discuss all Discussion points in this section. Roughly 8 minutes can be allocated to each Discussion point.

Discussion point 1. The need for Users’ Messages to be clear, simple and inclusive

8 minutes

Question:

Are the User Messages clear, simple and inclusive?

How could we enhance clarity, simplicity and inclusivity of the messages?

<i>Prompt for Table Host</i>	Two Messages in particular (<i>Draft Guidelines Message 3 and Guideline Message 4 – shown below</i>) had relatively lower agreement from Participants. It may be pertinent to spend some time examining these. What other ways could these messages support inclusivity for users?
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Discussion point 2. The need for Users Messages to be Practical and Relevant

8 minutes

Question: Are the User Messages Practical with respect helpful guidance of someone to be physically active and to reduce sedentary behaviour?

<i>Prompt for Table Host</i>	Qualitative data indicated that some participants felt that the Draft Messages for users could offer more practical advice and guidance for ‘doing’ physical activity if living with a long-term conditions. How could these Messages be enhanced to offer more practical support for users living with chronic conditions?
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Discussion point 3. The need for Users' Messages to be Motivational and Encouraging

8 minutes

Question: Are the User Messages designed in a way that fosters motivation for physical activity?

<i>Prompt for Table Host</i>	Qualitative data indicated that some participants felt that the Draft Messages for users could be framed in a more positive and motivational 'tone' at times. How can the current messages be enhanced to support motivation of people with long-term conditions?
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Session 3 Ends

Wrap-up

Are you living with a long-term health condition?

We want to hear from you!

South East Technological University on behalf of the HSE are developing the first national guidelines for Ireland to support physical activity for people living with chronic conditions - and we need ***your voice!***

Whether you're physically active or not active at all your views matter - help us ensure these guidelines reflect the needs of people living with chronic conditions from all backgrounds.

← **Take the Survey here!**

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Do you work with people with long-term health conditions?

Your expertise is needed!

South East Technological University on behalf of the HSE are developing the first national guidelines for Ireland to support physical activity for people living with chronic conditions - and we need ***your voice!***

If you're a physical activity, sports, health or social care professional who works with people with chronic conditions, we need your insights on shaping the national physical activity guidelines

← Take the Survey here!

The National Physical Activity and Sedentary Behaviour Guidelines for Ireland for People Living with Chronic Conditions

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